

D1.1 MultiX Perception 6G use cases, reference scenarios, requirements, and KPIs

MultiX

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the foundational outcomes of Task 1.1 within the MultiX project, which aims to revolutionize future 6G Radio Access Networks (RAN) through the MultiX Fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN System (MP6R). The document defines six representative use cases that demonstrate the integration of sensing and communication capabilities in diverse environments, including industrial robotics, smart homes, healthcare, UAV management, gesture recognition, and retail analytics. Each use case is analysed in terms of reference scenarios, service flows, functional and performance requirements, and regulatory considerations. The document also introduces expected Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), Key Values (KVs) and Key Value Indicators (KVI) to evaluate both technical efficiency and societal impact. These insights will guide the technical development in subsequent work packages and contribute to the standardization of Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) technologies in 6G networks.

Keywords

Use cases, sensing requirements, KPIs, KVs, KVI

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Acronyms and definitions

3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
AF	Application Function
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMR	Autonomous Mobile Robot
ANEC	European Association for the Coordination of Consumer Representation in Standardization
AoA	Angle of Arrival
AP	Access Point
BS	Base Station
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television Camera
CN	Core Network
CO	Carbon Monoxide
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
CPE	Customer Premises Equipment
CS	Communication Service
CSI	Channel State Information
DASH	Data Access and Security Hub
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment

DT	Digital Twin
E2E	End-to-End
EA	Ethics Advisor
EC	European Commission
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EMF	Electromagnetic Field
ESR	Ethics Evaluation Summary Report
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FR	Frequency Range
FRA	EU Agency for Fundamental Rights
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GR	Group Report
HCHO	Formaldehyde
HRV	Heart Rate Variability
ID	Identity Document
IEEE	Institute for Electric Electronic Engineers
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communications
ISG	Industry Specification Group

ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KV	Key Value
KVI	Key Value Indicator
LiDaR	Light Detection and Ranging
LoS	Line-of-Sight
MAC	Medium Access Control
MAG	Multistakeholder Advisory Group
MIMO	Multiple Input - Multiple Output
ML	Machine Learning
mmWave	Millimetre Wave
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MoCAP	Motion Capture
MP6R	MultiX Fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN System
MP6RC	MultiX Fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN System Controller
MPS	MultiX Perception System
NDT	Network Digital Twin
NO3	Nitrate
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing
OTFS	Orthogonal Time Frequency Space
PoC	Proof of Concept
QoS	Quality of Service

RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
REF	Reference
RF	Radio Frequency
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SO ₂	Sulphur Dioxide
SpO ₂	Oxygen saturation
STA	Station
THz	Terahertz
ToF	Time of Flight
TR	Technical Report
TSSA	Time-Synchronized Spatial Analysis
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UE	User Equipment
UK	United Kingdom
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications
UTM	Uncrewed Aerial System Traffic Management
VOC	Volatile Organic Compound
WP	Work Package

Table of partners

Short Name	Partner
UC3M	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
APP	Apple Technology Engineering BV&CO KG
OTE	ORGANISMOS TILEPIKOINONION TIS ELLADOS OTE AE
INT	Intel Deutschland GmbH
IDE	InterDigital Europe LTD
NEC	NEC Laboratories Europe GmbH
NEC Italia	NEC Italia S.p.A.
SAG	Siemens AG
TSA	Telefónica S.A.
TID	Telefónica Innovación Digital
BR	BubbleRAN
NXW	Nextworks
CNIT	Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le Telecomunicazioni
I2CAT	Fundació Privada i2CAT, Internet i Innovació digital a Catalunya
IMDEA	Fundación IMDEA Networks
IHP	IHP GmbH - Leibniz Institute for High Performance Microelectronics
IASA	Institute of Accelerating Systems and Applications
KUL	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
UC	Universidad de Cantabria

1 Executive summary

The MultiX Project aspires to redefine and revolutionize the design and operation of next-generation 3GPP Radio Access Networks (RAN) by introducing an innovative concept known as the MultiX Fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN System (MP6R). At the core of this vision are three key components: the MultiX Perception System (MPS), that introduces 3 levels of sensing functions into the RAN stack to support multi-sensor, multi-band, multi-static, and multi-technology Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC); the MP6R Controller (MP6RC) that extends the RAN control plane functionalities to coordinate and control multi-technology integration; and the Data Access and Security Hub (DASH) designed as a novel RAN data plane entity that aggregates multi-sensor data of diverse technologies, providing secure data access, processing, storage, and exposure.

Within this framework, the present deliverable constitutes the outcome of Task T1.1: “6G Perception Use Cases and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)”, which lays the foundational groundwork for the entire project. The purpose of this document is to establish a comprehensive set of use cases that illustrate potential 6G scenarios, alongside the definition of their KPIs, which serve as quantitative metrics for performance evaluation. These elements will play a crucial role in shaping the subsequent technical developments within Work Packages 2, 3, and 4 (WP2, WP3, and WP4) of the project, ensuring that the MultiX solution is appropriately tailored to address real-world demands and technological challenges.

We extend the two use cases that were identified during the project preparation phase and define four additional ones. For each defined use case, we specify: (i) a description of the use case; (ii) use cases found and related to the study case; (iii) example scenarios where the environmental and operational conditions under which the system is expected to function; (iv) preconditions as the needed circumstances or configurations required before activation; (v) service flows with the logical sequence of interactions and processes involved; (vi) postconditions with the expected outcomes and resulting system states; (vii) the functional requirements summarising the technical and operational specifications derived from each scenario; (viii) the KPIs; (ix) the Key Values (KVs) and Key Value Indicators (KVIs); (x) an explanation about their MultiX features; and finally (xi) the regulatory considerations ensuring that the development and deployment of MultiX technologies remain compliant with European legal standards and uphold principles of transparency, privacy, and accountability.

All in all, this deliverable defines the main use cases guiding the development of the MultiX system. The outcomes of Task T1.1 provide the foundation for subsequent technical work, allowing to set the basis for a sustainable, intelligent, and perception-driven 6G ecosystem.

2 Introduction

The evolution toward 6G marks a shift beyond traditional connectivity, aiming for intelligent, perceptive, and context-aware networks that unify communication, sensing, computing, and AI. This document presents the initial use cases, performance targets, and value indicators that underpin the technical development of the MultiX solution. Several use cases have also been submitted to 3GPP, highlighting the project's role in global standardization. The six defined use cases are summarized below:

- **Collaborative Robotics Supported by Multi-layer Digital Twin (DT):** Robots equipped with diverse sensors collaborate to perform complex industrial tasks, leveraging aggregated environmental data and the multi-layer DT for enhanced decision-making and adaptability.
- **Contact-free Health Monitoring:** Non-invasive sensing technologies enable real-time monitoring of vital signs and user localization in residential settings, improving safety and well-being without the need for wearable devices.
- **Smart Home Virtual Security:** ISAC-enabled networks provide seamless, tamper-proof security solutions for both indoor and outdoor environments, integrating multi-technology sensing directly into the 6G RAN architecture.
- **Low-altitude Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) Management:** Advanced sensing and network coordination support safe, efficient, and compliant UAV operations, addressing challenges in trajectory tracking, collision avoidance, and regulatory compliance.
- **Gesture Recognition in Industrial Environments:** Touchless interfaces using radio-based sensing enable intuitive and safe interaction between humans and robots in factory settings, improving productivity and safety.
- **Smart Shopping Tracker:** Indoor location analytics and collaborative sensing technologies enable retailers to understand customer behaviour and optimize store layouts, while ensuring privacy and data protection.

The first two use cases directly link to Proof-of-Concepts (PoCs), where key scenarios will be implemented and validated through experiments, targeting Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 4, while the remaining use cases will be characterized at a lower technology maturity level. This comprehensive definition represents the first phase of the MultiX project and serves as the foundation for the subsequent stages, shaping the MultiX system architecture, guiding the development of PoC trials, standardizing the technology and supporting further technical evaluations and implementations.

3 Use Cases

This section presents the MultiX use cases with unique performance and/or functional requirements unprecedented in any ETSI or 3GPP group or technical report. We take, as reference, the structure of Group Reports (GRs) / Technical Reports (TRs) of ETSI and 3GPP, but we go beyond it. Each use case provides a description of the technical challenges for MultiX and regulatory considerations in relation to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1] [2], Data Act [3] and AI Act [4].

Of all the identified use cases, the first two (industrial collaborative robots and contact-free human localization) will be analyzed in full detail, from identifying scenarios, requirements, KVs, KVIs and other factors, to conducting PoCs to validate their practical feasibility of some of their features, assess technical constraints, and determine the effort required for future implementation, reaching TRL 4 and showing integrated functionality under laboratory conditions.

Furthermore, several of the use cases presented in this deliverable have been formally contributed to 3GPP as part of ongoing efforts to influence and align with international standardization activities.

3.1 Industrial Collaborative Robots Supported by Multi-layer Digital Twin

3.1.1 Description of the use case

In this use case, robots collaborate to work on an industrial task together. They are supported by means of a Multi-layer Digital Twin and sensing capabilities of different kinds. These allow them to collaborate in sensing as well, supported by the DASH that collects sensing data from various sources. Each robot is equipped with specific sensors and capabilities, tailored to perform certain functions. However, the challenge lies in the fact that these robots, when operating individually, lack the comprehensive capability and information required to perform the industrial task successfully. Furthermore, they may derive only an incomplete picture of the surrounding environment with limited accuracy by sensing. The primary goal is to enable a group of robots to perform a task that surpasses their individual capabilities and to allow each robot to perceive its environment beyond its local sensory limitations. This is achieved through collaborative robots in both, operation and sensing.

An industrial environment delivers various pieces of information from sensors, which provide context information for different areas (e.g. different robots may have different sensing ranges) and topics (e.g. sensors for ranging vs. sensors for measuring radio channel characteristics). This sensor information may feed different Digital Twins through the DASH exposure interfaces, such as an Environment DT, a Network DT, and an Application DT. This is where the concept of a Multi-layer DT comes into play. Like the robots, each digital twin on its own lacks the capability to provide the full context that might be necessary for the industrial

application or communication service. The Multi-layer DT combines the individual digital twins to create a comprehensive view, that enables the identification and resolution of potential issues, improves decision-making, and allows for dynamic adaptations and reconfiguration of the industrial application or network, based on specific circumstances and predicted events. Especially, it can provide the updated environmental information to the robots. This is derived from the aggregated sensing results provided by the DASH and enhances the sensing capabilities of the individual robots and supports them in their collaboration and in other tasks that benefit from environmental information acquired by sensing methods.

In summary, the use case of collaborative robots in smart factories utilizing a Multi-layer Digital Twin exemplifies the power of combining individual capabilities to achieve a common goal. The Multi-layer DT provides a comprehensive and dynamic virtual representation using aggregated sensing results provided by the DASH through exposure interfaces. This empowers robots to collaborate by making joint decisions, adapting to changing conditions, and performing tasks beyond their individual capabilities. This collaborative approach leads to improved efficiency, productivity, and reliability in industrial applications.

3.1.2 Related use cases

Other examples of scenarios with collaborative robots are:

Cooperative Carrying in 3GPP TS 22.104

3GPP TS 22.104 [5] contains the use case of Cooperative Carrying. Here, large or heavy work pieces will be carried from one place to another by multiple mobile robots or Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) in a smart factory. These mobile robots / AGVs need to work together to carry the large or heavy work piece safely. This cooperation is achieved with a cyber-physical control application that controls the drives and movements of the mobile robots/AGVs in a coordinated way, so that large or heavy work pieces are carried smoothly and safely from one place to another.

The use case of Cooperative Carrying targets direct communication between the mobile robots/AGVs. The direct communication has to support industrial traffic (URLLC and time synchronization). There is no sensing as anticipated in MultiX involved.

Cooperative Carrying Robots in 5G-ACIA

The concept of cooperative carrying robots was first introduced in the context of 5G-enabled smart factory use cases. The idea is that AGVs can work together to transport large, heavy, and fragile workpieces across the factory floor. To enable this, 5G sidelink communication was identified as the most suitable approach for maintaining a stable wireless connection among collaborative mobile robots or AGVs, which typically operate in close proximity [6].

Each mobile robot or AGV integrates a 5G User Equipment (UE) to support sidelink communication. The automation application running on these robots establishes the 5G sidelink connection. When robots gather around a workpiece, they form a collaborative group

based on essential information such as group formation parameters, 5G radio configuration, and a synchronized clock domain to ensure deterministic communication.

The required transmission range for stringent industrial 5G sidelink communication depends on the size of the workpiece. For large workpieces, a range of up to 50 meters may suffice, while smaller workpieces can be handled within shorter ranges, such as 10 or 25 meters. For very large workpieces, communication ranges of up to 100 meters could be achieved by introducing an intermediate mobile robot or AGV acting as a relay.

6G-ANNA – Cooperative collaborative robots

AGVs and Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs) are key applications in cyber-physical systems. In the 6G-ANNA [7] use case Cooperative Collaborative Robots, multiple AMRs or AGVs jointly transport large, heavy, and fragile workpieces across a factory floor. Their coordination is achieved through a control application that synchronizes drives and motion. This scenario imposes stringent requirements on reliability and latency, with delays limited to a few milliseconds and packet loss probabilities as low as 10^{-6} to 10^{-8} . Requirements vary depending on the workpiece type—fragile items like glass panes demand higher precision compared to elastic materials such as rubber blocks. To meet these demands, the concept of subnetworks was introduced in the 6G-ANNA project, ensuring localized resource allocation and high-frequency reuse within the swarm's spatial footprint. Each subnetwork can operate autonomously or under centralized control via a master AMR, while robots must remain functional even during communication loss. Additional considerations include deploying a campus private network or a dedicated network slice to prevent external intrusion and integrating ISAC for route planning and collision detection. The idea was to demonstrate how subnetwork-based architecture enhances reliability, scalability, and adaptability for collaborative robotics in future 6G-enabled factories.

Hexa-X-II – Representative Use Case Collaborating Mobile Robots

This description is taken from the corresponding Hexa-X-II deliverable [8].

At the centre of this representative use case of the Collaborative Robots use case family of Hexa-X-II [8] are autonomous robots with the ability to move, sense their environment, and perform a productive task collaboratively. These robots can communicate with each other, with other machines, and with nearby humans to perform individual tasks that contribute to a common cooperative objective. The purpose of the communication is safety and cooperation, to enable a group of robots to perform tasks beyond their individual capabilities, but potentially also helping people to perform tasks irrespective of their current capabilities. This includes to enable individual robots to perceive their environment beyond their local capabilities. Scenarios within this use case family may include industrial manufacturing campuses, smart workshops, cooperative carrying with mobile robots, lot-size-1 production, automated industrial tasks, construction sites, agriculture, and smart living.

The use case Cooperating Mobile Robots focuses primarily on local ad hoc connectivity between cooperating robots embedded in private networks. In this context, the network of the

future is envisioned to enable local cooperation among robots, to support autonomous task-solving by the robots, to enhance the safety of human-machine interaction, and to ensure that only authorized machines and humans can participate in task solving. Multiple robots form a communication cluster or subnetwork for the following purposes:

- Coordinating and controlling their actions for successful collaborative task execution.
- Exchanging raw or processed sensor data.
- Sharing AI/ML models, weights, and federated learning.
- Ensuring safety for humans nearby in the event of an emergency.
- Potentially connect to other local capacities such as edge computing, building sensor data, digital twins, AI servers, etc.

The KPIs for Collaborative Mobile Robots include position KPIs of different degree ≤ 1 m. Sensing related capabilities are required for capturing the environmental context, but no specific KPIs are given. Network-integrated sensing may complement dedicated onboard sensors. Efficient transport of data/information from connected external sensors is needed.

Further related Use Cases from European Projects

Table 1 shows some sensing performance requirements of related use cases defined in other European projects.

Table 1. Sensing performance requirements of related use cases in other projects for the industrial collaborative robots use case

Project Use Cases	Confidence (%)	Positioning (m)	Velocity (km/h)	Resolution (m or km/h)	Max. latency (ms)	Refreshing rate (ms)	Missed detection	False alarm	REF
Hexa-X		< 1	10	~10 m and 0.36 km/h		100 to 0.1			[9]
Hexa-X II Cooperating Mobile Robots, Network Assisted Mobility, Real-time	90 to >99	Fine: <0.10 Coarse : <1 Human presence: 0.4	< 20						[10] [8]

Digital Twins									
Opti-6G	99.999	< 1		< 100 m and 10.8 km/h	10 RTT				[11]
Komsens 6G		Sub-cm to dm range		0.20 - 1 m		100 - 10			[12]

3.1.3 Example scenarios

Figure 1. Example scenario for collaborating robots in smart factories supported by Multi-Layer DT

Figure 1 shows an example scenario for collaborating robots in a smart factory. Robot B has to move to Robot A to work collaboratively on a task. The different local sensing results of both robots are aggregated in the DASH and provided to the Multi-layer DT. The aggregated sensing

information provides guidance for the movement of Robot B, e.g. path routing, detection of obstacles and openings, as well as optimal connectivity. Robot B can now see beyond the wall that hides Robot A, it can determine a path around the wall, and sensing information in the Multi-layer DT is used to provide reliable connectivity with the needed Quality of Service (QoS), by dynamically adapting, for instance, the reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS) on the right-hand side in Figure 1.

3.1.4 Preconditions

In the factory, a private 6G network (non-public network) has been set up. The robots are connected to it with one or multiple, different RATs.

Robot B (see Figure 1) must carry a workpiece to Robot A to work on it collaboratively.

3.1.5 Service flows

The obstacle is moving between Robots A and B (see Figure 1). The obstacle obstructs both the communication and the movement of Robot B.

Robots A and B have been continuously sending their sensing information to the Multi-Layer DT. The sensing information comes from the ISAC functionality of the available RATs at Robots A and B as well as from other sources of sensing information such as Lidars, cameras, and machine vision.

Based on the received sensing information, the Multi-Layer DT combines the information from the environment DT and the network DT (NDT). The result and derived predictions on UE connectivity (NDT) are used to update the intra-logistics path for Robot B as well as the network configuration to maintain connectivity with Robot B in the dynamic environment.

The 6G system configures the RIS so that communication with Robot B will be maintained.

The combination of the sensing information of Robots A and B results in a more complete environmental model of the relevant areas around Robot A and B. Relevant parts of this enhanced environmental model are transmitted to Robots A and B. This enhances their sensing capabilities.

The intra-logistics path of Robot B is updated based on the pathways, obstacles, and openings detected by sensing. The update is done either by Robot B itself based on the enhanced sensing information / enhanced model of the environment received from the Multi-Layer DT, or by the Multi-Layer DT, that sends the resulting intra-logistics path to Robot B.

3.1.6 Postconditions

Robot B travelled successfully to Robot A in the dynamic environment with moving obstacles (see Figure 1). Robots A and B work collaboratively on the workpiece provided by Robot B.

3.1.7 Functional requirements

[FR1-1] Timely delivery of sensing data, embracing location and surrounding information (i.e. obstacles) of robots as well as signal strength in the coverage area to network management solutions.

[FR1-2] The (private) 6G network shall be able to configure and control sensing-enabled network devices such as base stations (BS), Wi-Fi Customer Premises Equipment (CPEs), and UEs.

[FR1-3] The (private) 6G network shall be able to collect 6G and non-6G sensing-related information from sensing-enabled network devices in a DASH and Multi-layer DT.

[FR1-4] The (private) 6G network shall be able to fuse 6G and non-6G sensing data.

[FR1-5] The (private) 6G network shall be able to dynamically reconfigure network devices based on aggregated sensing information from the Multi-layer DT to provide reliable connectivity with the required Quality of Service. In particular, MAC schedulers are expected to (re-)allocate radio resources anticipating communication impairments.

[FR1-6] The 6G system shall provide interfaces to be able to provide sensing results to an environment digital twin / multi-layer digital twin.

[FR1-7] The 6G system shall provide interfaces to be able to re-configure network devices for continuous connectivity of UEs based on information received from a network digital twin.

3.1.8 Performance requirements

The performance requirements for this use case are summarized in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2. Performance requirements for collaborating robots in smart factories supported by Multi-Layer DT Use Case

Scenario	Sensing service area	Confidence level [%]	Accuracy of positioning estimate by sensing (for a target confidence level) (note 3)		Accuracy of velocity estimate by sensing (for a target confidence level)		Sensing resolution		Max sensing service latency [ms]	Refreshing rate [s]	Missed detection [%] (note 1)	False alarm [%] (note 1)
			Horizontal [m]	Vertical [m]	Horizontal [m/s]	Vertical [m/s]	Range resolution [m] (note 3)	Velocity resolution (horizontal/ vertical) [m/s x m/s]				
Sensing of Surroundings	Indoor (Factory Environment)	99	0.1	n/a	0.1	n/a	0.5 to 1	1.5	≤100	0.1	< 10%	< 10%
Detection of Pathways	Indoor (Factory Environment)	99	0.25	0.25	0.1	n/a	0.75	1.5	≤100	0.1	< 10%	< 10%

NOTE 1: Only valid for non-time-critical applications, < 1% if integrated in time-critical processes.

NOTE 2: A maximum sensing range of 10 m is required.

NOTE 3: In this table, accuracy of positioning estimate is the horizontal or vertical minimum distance between distinguishable objects, range resolution is the minimum distance between distinguishable objects regarding depth sensing.

Table 3. Performance requirements for collaborating robots in smart factories supported by Multi-Layer DT Use Case

CS availability: target value (%)	CS reliability : mean time between failures	End-to-end latency: maximum	Service bit rate: user experienced data rate	Message size [byte]	Transfer interval : target value	Survival time	UE speed	# of UEs	Service area	Remarks
99.999	4 h	< 20 ms	Sensing Result: 1 Mbit/s Sensing Data: 2.5 Gbit/s	15 kByte 50 kByte	100 ms	Not considered	1.5 m/s	≤ 10	100 m x 50 m x 10 m	Sensing Information: Robot → Multi-Layer DT
99.999	4 h	5 ms to 10 ms	10 Mbit/s per stream, up to 2.5 Gbit/s for multi-camera sensing	4 MByte	33 ms	Not considered	1.5 m/s	≤ 10	100 m x 50 m x 10 m	Video Sensing: (Robot → Multi-Layer DT) [13]
99.999	4 h	5 ms to 10 ms	10 Mbit/s per stream	1 MByte to 5 MByte	100 ms	Not considered	1.5 m/s	≤ 10	100 m x 50 m x 10 m	Sensing-result-related application data (Multi-Layer DT → Robot)
CS – Communication Service										

3.1.9 KVs and KVIs

The use case “Industrial Collaborative Robots Supported by Multi-layer Digital Twin” relates mainly to key values “Economical Sustainability and Innovation” and “Privacy and Confidentiality”. Furthermore, there is some indirect relation to key value “Environmental Sustainability”. Moreover, single KVIs are related to key values “Personal Health and Protection from Harm”, “Societal Sustainability”, and “Trust”.

Environmental Sustainability

Energy efficiency is a general requirement of any industrial production process and any industrial communication network including Industrial 6G networks, multi-layer digital twins, and multi-sensorial 6G perception systems. Collaboration in sensing of the use case allows to deploy sensing with less accuracy using less energy but still receiving high-quality sensing results. Waste reduction is part of the actual production process not considered nor evaluated in the MultiX use case “Industrial Collaborative Robots Supported by Multi-layer Digital Twin”. Similar relation is true for preserving a high-quality natural environment in and around the factory.

How to measure: Energy usage in sensing, transportation processes, data transfers, and data storage.

Target KVI: reduced energy consumption compared to (a) use case without sensing and (b) high precision sensing vs. combined less accuracy sensing and post processing.

Societal Sustainability

Automation in dynamic environments and increased use of autonomous mobile devices may lead to a reduced workforce on the factory floor. As a consequence, responsible measures need to be taken, for instance providing additional training and education for new job profiles.

How to measure: number of (a) jobs reduced, (b) new jobs created, (c) retrained/upskilled workers.

Target KVI: 100% of workers from lost work roles retrained/upskilled or in new jobs created. No worker became unemployed.

Economical Sustainability and Innovation

Improved collaboration and industrial processes are achieved through a Multi-sensorial Perception System using a Multi-Layer Digital Twin. The Multi-Layer Digital Twin provides economical benefits and improvements.

Operational improvements and technological advancements drive productivity and sustainability.

Automated mobile industrial units, especially AMRs and AGVs can be increasingly used in industrial activities.

How to measure: New revenue opportunities with MultiX perception system.

Target KVI: Increase of revenue by use of MultiX perception system.

Operational cost savings

The use case provides collaboration between autonomous devices. This allows dynamic adaptation to the environment on the factory floor. The support by the Multi-Layer DT provides optimal routes and process execution.

How to measure: Costs of dynamic adaptations of the production process

Target KVI: Decreased costs of dynamic adaptations of the production process due to use of MultiX perception system for automated collaboration between autonomous devices.

Privacy and Confidentiality

Humans might be present at the factory floor in some specific situations. They are part of the sensed factory environment. In such situations, the perception system needs to detect them as humans but shall not identify them individually.

How to measure: regular supervision of GDPR compliance, number of privacy breaches, amount of personal data collected (data points, Gbytes) and storage duration.

Target KVI: 100% GDPR and ethics compliance; no privacy breaches, no privacy concerns raised during operation. Minimal amount of personal data and minimal storage duration.

Simplified Life

The autonomous mobile industrial units will take off transportation tasks from human workers.

How to measure: ratio of transportation tasks provided by autonomous mobile industrial units.

Target KVI: >95% of transportation tasks are provided by autonomous mobile industrial units.

Personal health and protection from harm

If humans are present at the factory floor, the electromagnetic fields (EMF) exposure of the humans due to RF sensing needs to be below allowed regulatory limits.

How to measure: EMF exposure.

Target KVI: EMF exposure below regulatory limits for humans.

Trust

There needs to be trust into a reliable autonomous functionality of the industrial machines, AMRs, and AGVs. In case of missed detections or false alarms, the AMRs/AGVs need to stop in a safe state. No accidents with humans must happen, nor accidents with objects on the factory floor, to avoid financial losses due to damages and stopped production.

How to measure: Costs due to false alarms and missed detections, number of accidents, uptime / downtime of normal operation.

Target KVI: availability, <10% false alarms, <1% missed detections. Additional costs due to stopped or delayed production no accidents, no persons injured, no damage due to malfunction.

User Acceptance and Perceived Trustworthiness

The use case is set in an autonomous factory environment. Workers might be in this factory environment. This KV relates to how willing and confident workers are about the collaborative sensing, and whether they trust its operation and purpose.

How to measure: Survey among workers on their perceived trustworthiness of the factory environment using the MultiX perception system.

Target KVI: no serious concerns, ≥80% full user acceptance.

Non-intrusiveness

This KV relates to how seamlessly the system of sensing collaboration and support by multi-layer digital twins operates in the background without requiring any action by the worker on the factory floor.

How to measure: User rating of intrusiveness (e.g., 1 to 5 scale), number of interactions with MultiX system by worker.

Target KVI: ≤ 2 out of 5 average intrusiveness rating (1 = best value), ≤ 12 interactions per hour

3.1.10 Specific MultiX features

The use case “Industrial Collaborative Robots Supported by Multi-layer Digital Twin” will integrate different sensor information from various sources. This integration is enabled by MultiX’ approach of the MultiX Perception System (MPS) and the Data Access and Security Hub (DASH).

The aggregated sensing information will be used by a combination of various Digital Twins to get a comprehensive view on the environment, the production process, and the context (e.g., 3D physical world + wireless signal quality across space). This is enabled within MultiX by the Data Access and Security Hub (DASH) and the Multi-layer Digital Twin approach.

The multi-sensorial perception and the aggregation of sensing information and their combination in the multi-layer digital twin enable making decisions for dynamic configurations and adaptations of production tasks, mobility paths, and resource allocations and traffic flows in the communication network. This process is supported by AI/ML tools to avoid the introduction of unnecessary idle times during task execution. Interfaces between the MultiX DASH and the different digital twins and their equivalent in the real world, e.g. between a network digital twin and the communication network, support the dynamic configuration.

The use case “Industrial Collaborative Robots Supported by Multi-layer Digital Twin” is the basis for MultiX Proof of Concept “Multi-layer Network Digital Twin for Industrial Manufacturing” [14].

This use case has been provided to 3GPP SA1 as contributions:

- [S1-253316](#) / [S1-253513](#), “New use case on Collaborating Robots in Smart Factories (Siemens, OTE, InterDigital) to the 3GPP SA1 Meeting #111,
- [S1-254247](#) / [S1-254396](#), “New Use Case on Robots Collaborating in Sensing in Smart Factories - Re-submission” to the 3GPP SA1 Meeting #112,

and is included in 3GPP TR 22.870 “Study on 6G Use Cases and Service Requirements” as use case on robots collaborating in sensing in smart factories.

3.1.11 Regulatory considerations

This section provides regulatory considerations with respect to GDPR [1], the Data Act [3] and the AI Act [4].

Table 4 presents the GDPR roles and responsibilities for this use case.

Table 4. GDPR Roles and Responsibilities in the Industrial Collaborative Robots Use Case

Role	Who	Description
Data Subject	Workers present at the factory floor	Workers might be present at the factory floor in specific situations. They need to be detected as part of the environment
Data Controller	Factory operator	Determines the purpose of the production and the necessary means for performing the required steps. This includes involvement of human workers
Data Processor	Operator of the Private industrial communication network, Multi-layer DT operator	The sensing information is transmitted over the private communication network of the factory, processing of the data is done in the DASH and the Multi-layer DT. The DASH and the Multi-layer DT will aggregate and process various sensing information and derive input for the different digital twins, especially for a model of the factory environment that might include workers

Table 5 shows the key aspects of the Data Act in relation with this use case.

Table 5. Key Aspects of the Data Act and Description in Relation to the Industrial Collaborative Robots Use Case

Aspect	Description
Fair Access and Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factory-internal data • Sensing results and derived data will be made available to workers as part of their job duties • Sensing results are made available to multi-layer digital twin to perform production tasks • Access to personal data on request needs to be provided
Data Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factory-internal data • Sensing Data generated and transmitted by private factory network and processed by multi-layer digital

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> twin (factory-operated or provided by external service operator) Data-sharing with relevant official partners with respect to safety and in case of (near) accidents if required
Consumer Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal data of workers must not be made available to third parties
Business Protections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data must be secure and privacy protected. Sensing results and network configurations might be considered some sort of trade secret since they may provide unwanted insights to competitors Data processing shall be on-premises. DASH and Multi-layer digital twin must be privacy-protected and trustworthy if located outside the factory premises or operated by service provider
Interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interfaces for interoperable exchange of sensing data, sensing results, and dynamic configurations and adaptations of production tasks, mobility paths, and resource allocations and traffic flows in the communication network between factory communication network and multi-layer digital twin

Table 6 provides the risk classification of the sensing data processing in this use case in relation with the AI Act.

Table 6. AI-Enabled Technologies in the Industrial Collaborative Robots Use Case and their Risk Classification

Technology Enabled by AI	Risk Classification	Explanation
Sensing Data Processing	Minimal	No interaction with humans. Backup safety mechanisms in AGVs, etc.

3.2 Contact-free human localization and vital signs detection

3.2.1 Definition of the use case

This use case addresses non-invasive health monitoring in indoor residential environments using ISAC capabilities within advanced wireless networks (e.g., 5G-Advanced or 6G), combined with other sensors, when available. It aims to enhance personal safety and well-being—particularly for elderly individuals or patients with chronic or mobility-limiting

conditions—through contact-free detection of vital signs and user localization without the need for wearable devices.

The monitored environment is equipped either with a mobile robot carrying the sensing devices and a single antenna, or with multiple distributed static antennas (N antennas), forming a dense sensing topology. These antennas establish several radio frequency (RF) links (M links), resulting in either a fully digital or hybrid sensing architecture, depending on the N-to-M ratio. Human users are typically at rest or asleep, with their User Equipment (UE) remaining static during the monitoring session. Monitoring may be performed either:

- **Occasional**, when requested (e.g., before sleep).
- **Periodic**, based on pre-set intervals (e.g., overnight).

The collected sensing data is processed locally or at the edge through a perception engine to determine respiration patterns, heartbeat, motion status, and location. Anomalies such as irregular breathing or lack of motion can trigger real-time alerts to caregivers or emergency services.

The MULTIX project supports this use case by providing a multi-static testbed infrastructure, real-time AI-enabled perception systems, and a secure data access architecture that enable proof-of-concept (PoC) validation and contribute to standardization activities for ISAC-based eHealth solutions.

3.2.2 Related use cases

We have a two-dimensional comparison of state-of-the-art use cases, one is from standardization organizations (including 3GPP, ETSI), and the other is from other European projects (such as Hexa-X and Hexa-X II).

3GPP TR 22.837 [15]

- *Use case on health monitoring at home*: Focuses on detecting events such as falls, lack of movement, and abnormal health patterns using wireless sensing systems deployed in residential environments.
- *Use case on contactless sleep monitoring service*: Describes a system for monitoring sleep states and vital signs without requiring wearable devices, mainly using in-room sensors and smart devices.
- *Use case on service continuity of unobtrusive health monitoring*: Addresses challenges in ensuring seamless monitoring across different locations or network conditions without requiring user intervention.

ETSI (ETSI GR ISC 001) [16]

- *Use case on human motion recognition*: Similar in scope to the 3GPP case, focusing on indoor motion analysis using non-contact methods for smart environments and safety.

- *Use case on body proximity sensor:* Describes the use of sensors to detect human proximity to a device or area, primarily for user interface, automation, or access control scenarios.

Hexa-X [17] and Hexa-X-II Projects [10]

- *Local trust zones for human & machine:* Using topical, implanted, injected or ingested sensors and devices, continuous health monitoring can be performed and adjustive measures can be implemented if needed, such as medicine dispensers. A 6G tele-medical paradigm will be enabled by in-body sensing and analytics in conjunction with a wide area connectivity option.
- *Physical awareness:* Refers to systems that sense human presence, posture, or gestures, typically for ambient intelligence or responsive environments.
- *Trusted environments:* Focuses on secure, privacy-preserving sensing and communication, aligning with healthcare needs for trusted monitoring platforms.

Figure 2. Contact-free human localization and vital signs detection scenarios 1 and 2

Short description: Use case illustration in the first two representative scenarios is shown in Figure 2, where Scenario 1 considers a seated person with a potential interferer in a living room or meeting room, while Scenario 2 focuses on a sleeping person in a bedroom. Scenario 1 will first conduct localization of multiple persons, then estimate the breathing of the user; Scenario 2 will be constantly monitoring the breathing. Both scenarios assume UEs (smartphones) are static.

Figure 3. Contact-free human localization and vital signs detection scenario 3

Short description: Scenario 3, shown in Figure 3, in the use case considers a static person in an arbitrary location, monitored using the mobile robot, which serves as a localizable moving platform for the vital signs monitorization equipment.

3.2.3 Example scenarios

This use case targets several representative scenarios of non-contact health monitoring in a home environment, enabled by distributed wireless sensing. Scenarios 1 and 2 show how we consider two representative scenarios to show the focus of the use case for the static antenna deployment, while Scenario 3 shows the mobile robot approach. Last but not least, we consider investigating the role of AI in health monitoring in the Scenario 4, with a focus on the real-time responsiveness, which requires not only the fast processing of data using the AI, but the timely response/alerts from the network side.

Scenario 1: Breathing of sitting user with interferer

During the daytime, the same individual spends time seated in a room chair. The system continuously monitors:

- Respiratory signals, especially shallow breathing or long periods of inactivity.
- Location information of multiple persons, especially for interferers (other people) in the environment.

The user does not interact with any device, however, for validation, markers of motion capture cameras may be installed on the chest to track the movements led by breathing. Multi-antenna signals are coordinated across distributed sensing nodes. Time-series trends in location and respiration are logged to support preventive care.

Scenario 2: Contact-Free Sleep Monitoring

A person is sleeping in their bedroom during the night. Distributed antennas installed in the room form multiple RF links using FR2 or FR1 bands. The system passively monitors:

- Respiratory rate and irregular breathing patterns, using micro-Doppler shifts and signal reflections detected across multiple links.
- Sudden anomalies, such as cessation of breathing or unexpected motion (e.g., a fall from bed).

All sensing data is mainly processed by the MPS, and alerts are generated via the DASH component if critical health events are detected. No wearable device is required, and the phone (UE) remains static on a nearby surface.

Scenario 3: Mobile Robot-Based Measurement System

A mobile robot platform is deployed to follow a target individual across different smart home locations. The robot autonomously navigates to maintain proximity to the user, but measurement operations are only performed when the robot is stationary. The system includes:

- Single onboard antenna for wireless connectivity and data transmission.
- GPS and other sensors to complement smart home localization and ensure accurate positioning and vital signs measurement.

During operation, the robot tracks the user's position and pauses at predefined intervals or when viable measurement conditions are met. At each stop, the system collects:

- Physiological signals (e.g., respiration, heart rate).
- Environmental data (e.g., temperature, humidity).
- Location and timestamp metadata for contextual analysis.

All data is processed locally or transmitted to a central server for fusion and interpretation. The robot resumes tracking after each measurement cycle, enabling dynamic monitoring without requiring the user to wear any device.

Scenario 4: AI-Assisted Health & Safety Monitoring for the Elderly (to be demonstrated in Athens, Greece by OTE and IASA)

This scenario addresses the need for a next-generation health and safety monitoring specifically useful for elderly individuals, to provide users, their families and caregivers with peace of mind. By leveraging cutting-edge technologies, the related App will track vital health metrics for the elderly, their movement patterns, as well as environmental factors to ensure timely event detection, timely intervention and enhanced quality of life.

The key features of the particular scenario, which OTE and IASA plan to demonstrate in Athens, Greece, include:

Real-Time Motion and Location Tracking

mmWave-enabled PIR sensors and/or Wi-Fi signals will be exploited to provide detailed insights, including the person's location within specific zones of the room/house, motion detection within user-defined areas, real-time tracking of movement patterns, allowing to understand daily routines and identify deviations from normal behaviour, falls and/or collapses.

Near Real-Time Health Data Monitoring

A wide range of health metrics, typically from wearable devices will be collected, such as

- steps today, step length, distance travelled, walking speed, walking asymmetry, active energy expenditure, exercise time and stairs climbed.
- key heart/health indicators such as current heart rate, resting heart rate, walking heart rate, heart rate variability (HRV), respiratory rate and blood oxygen saturation (SpO2) levels.

This data will be continuously monitored, and intelligent algorithms will be applied to detect anomalies that could indicate potential health issues, providing real-time alerts whenever the measurements fall outside the normal ranges.

Real-Time Alerts and Emergency Notifications

To ensure the user's safety alerts will be sent, in real-time, in case of data unavailability (if the smartwatch or health tracking data is not available for an extended period), or in case of anomalous health events (detection of irregular/abnormal health metrics). The alerts will be sent in real-time to the caregivers / first-responders and/or the family members, who shall take immediate action.

Smart Home Integration for Emergency Response

In the event of an alert, first-responders/ caregivers (and/or family members) will be provided with the following capabilities:

- High service quality at their current location and while on the move e.g., through network slicing and/or immediate access network re-configuration.
- Live video footage from (typical) IP cameras installed in the house, allowing the “responders” to visually assess the situation before acting.
- Remote door unlocking: Using a secure passcode (that will have been received via the initial alert message or upon request), the “responders” can unlock the main door (via a mobile app), allowing them to access the home without delay in case of an emergency.
- Smart glasses integration: The first responders will be equipped with smart glasses, that will enable them to share video footage to other first-responders or medical professionals at the hospital for consultation.

AI-Powered Movement Prediction and Activity Monitoring

Based on the data collected either from PIR sensors and/or from Wi-Fi-based positioning, the mobile app will predict the user's next movement or detect if remained stationary for an unusually long period of time. This predictive capability will help ensure that the elderly is active (and moving regularly). Long inactivity will trigger a check-in alert to caregivers or first responders.

Environmental Monitoring (Air-Quality sensors)

Poor indoor air quality can seriously affect the health and comfort, especially of elderly individuals. As people age, their respiratory and immune systems become more sensitive, making them more vulnerable to pollutants like dust, mold, pet dander, and VOCs from cleaning products or furniture. Prolonged exposure can lead to aggravated asthma, chronic bronchitis, fatigue, headaches and even cardiovascular issues. The mobile app will integrate air-quality sensors (such as: CO₂, CO, HCHO, SO₂, NO₃, etc.) to issue alerts and recommendations (to the individuals, caregivers, family members), when required. Alerts may include recommendations for ventilation and air-filtration in cases of high CO₂ concentrations. Additional sensors - to further increase safety - such as smoke, gas or water leaks could be also added.

3.2.4 Preconditions

- The user is subscribed to a health monitoring service enabled by ISAC technologies.
- For scenarios 1 and 2, the environment (e.g., bedroom or living room) is equipped with distributed sensing antennas supporting FR1 and/or FR2 bands.
- For scenario 3, the environment is navigable by the mobile robot.
- A compatible UE (e.g., smartphone) remains static and assists in sensing or provide a reference signal.
- A network-based perception function processes sensing data and extracts features such as breathing rate and location status.
- The user has consented to non-intrusive monitoring, with data secured and shared only with authorized entities.
- For scenario 4, the environment (e.g., bedroom, kitchen, living room) is equipped with Wi-Fi and a variety of sensors is utilized, including PIR sensors, IP cameras, smartwatch sensors, IoT environmental sensors, as well as smart locks.

3.2.5 Service flows

- The monitoring system initializes and retrieves user-specific sensing preferences.
- The UE (phone) transmits uplink pilots for sensing, and distributed antennas receive signals that include reflected signals from the human body or interferer.
- Multi-static (or multi-band) sensing data is synchronized and processed for location and respiration detection using advanced signal processing or AI.

- An alert is generated if anomalies such as immobility or abnormal respiration are detected.
- Results are sent securely to authorized users (family, healthcare providers).

3.2.6 Postconditions

- The user's health status and location are determined.
- Alerts are generated in a timely and reliable manner.
- All data is securely stored and processed with privacy compliance.

3.2.7 Functional requirements

To support reliable, contact-free monitoring of human presence, posture, and respiration in indoor environments, the system must fulfill the following functional requirements:

[FR2-1] The wireless system shall support coordinated sensing across distributed RAN nodes and UEs to enable high-resolution localization and vital sign monitoring in indoor environments.

[FR2-2] The system shall enable non-intrusive respiration monitoring (e.g., breathing rate) based on RF signal reflections from human subjects without requiring wearable devices.

[FR2-3] The system shall allow a UE in static mode (e.g., a phone placed near the user) to participate in wireless sensing and share its sensing data with the network.

[FR2-4] The system shall support multi-band and multi-technology integration (e.g., FR1, FR2, non-3GPP sensors) to enhance robustness and adaptability to varying indoor layouts

[FR2-5] The system shall support real-time fusion and analysis of sensing data at the network edge to enable timely anomaly detection (e.g., apnea, inactivity, fall).

[FR2-6] The system shall ensure data privacy and security by implementing local processing and controlled data sharing through secure access hubs (e.g., DASH).

[FR2-7] The system shall support configurable monitoring modes (e.g., scheduled, continuous, or on-demand) tailored to the user's health profile and activity context.

[FR2-8] The system shall be able to generate alerts and share actionable information with authorized caregivers or emergency services in case of detected health-critical events.

3.2.8 Performance requirements

Table 7 shows the technical requirements specifically for health monitoring.

Table 7. Performance requirements for Contact-Free Human Localization and Respiration Detection Use Case

KPI Name	Description	Target Value / Metric	Relevance to Use Case
Localization Accuracy	Accuracy of detecting human position indoors	≤ 0.5 m	Required for reliable location detection
Respiration Rate Estimation Accuracy	Error in measuring breaths per minute	$\leq \pm 1$ breaths/min	Critical for vital sign monitoring, especially during sleep
Max. detection Latency	Time from sensing anomaly to alert generation	≤ 2 s (0.1-5 s in 3GPP)	Ensures timely intervention during critical events (e.g., fall, apnea)
Breathing stoppages duration	Duration of breathing stoppages triggered alerts	≥ 10 s	Ensures timely intervention for anomalies of breathing
False Positive Rate (Anomaly Detection)	Rate of incorrectly triggered alerts	$\leq 3\%$	Ensures trust and reduces unnecessary healthcare interventions
False Negative Rate	Rate of missed critical health or motion events	$\leq 1\%$	High reliability for health-critical monitoring
Coverage Area per Setup	Physical space monitored by one MultiX setup	≥ 5 m ²	Efficiency of deployment in typical residential environments
Edge Processing Latency	Time required by MPS/DASH to process and fuse sensor data	≤ 100 ms	Supports real-time responsiveness and scalability
Energy Consumption (UE standby)	Power used by static UE during passive monitoring	$\leq 5\%$ daily battery drain	Ensures long-term usability for static UE scenarios
Refreshing rate	Rate of the sensing refreshing over monitoring periods	≤ 0.1 s	Ensures monitoring continuity, especially overnight

Table 8 shows the technical requirements for sensing.

Table 8. Performance requirements for Sensing and Positioning for Contact-Free Human Localization and Respiration Detection Use Case

KPI Name	Target Value / Metric
Confidence level	$\geq 95\%$
Positioning [m]	Horizontal: 0.5–1 m; Vertical: 0.5–1 m
Velocity [m/s]	Horizontal: ≤ 1.5 m/s; Vertical: ≤ 1.5 m/s
Max sensing service latency	< 2000 ms
Refreshing rate	≤ 1 s
Missed detection	$\leq 10\%$
False alarm	$\leq 2\%$

3.2.9 KVs and KVIs

User Acceptance and Perceived Trustworthiness

This KVI measures how willing end users are to adopt the proposed vital signs monitoring solution, and whether they trust its operation and purpose. This KVI relates with MultiX goal to demonstrate a user-centric wireless sensing solution.

How to measure: Pre- and post-pilot surveys on trust, comfort, and likelihood of continued use.

Target KVI: $\geq 80\%$ of surveyed users express trust and willingness to adopt.

Perceived and Real Privacy Preservation

This KVI evaluates both the actual protection of personal data (e.g., no identifiable information collected) and how users perceive their privacy is protected. This KVI relates with MultiX goal to ensure the provision of GDPR-compliant and ethically aligned sensing services.

How to measure: User feedback on perceived data exposure.

Target KVI: 100% GDPR and ethics compliance; $\leq 10\%$ of users raise privacy concerns post-demonstration.

Healthcare Impact and Preventive Value

This KVI measures the degree to which the system enables early detection of dangerous events (apnea, long inactivity, falls) and reduces emergency incidents.

How to measure: Reduction in number of unreported or late-detected events (pre/post comparison over pilot window).

Target KVI: $\geq 25\%$ reduction in undetected critical events in monitored homes.

Non-intrusiveness

This KVI measures how seamlessly the system operates in the background without requiring cameras, active sensors, or any action required by the user. This KVI relates with MultiX goal to develop non-invasive sensing methods using existing infrastructure.

How to measure: User rating of intrusiveness (e.g., 1-5 scale).

Target KVI: $\leq 2/5$ average intrusiveness rating.

Contribution to Public Safety and Wellbeing

This KVI assesses the broader impact of the proposed vital signs monitoring service on community safety, perceived security, and quality of life. This KVI relates with MultiX goal to improve real-time situational awareness for safety.

How to measure: Before/after statistics on security incidents in pilot areas. Feedback from local authorities or citizen associations.

Target KVI: 20-30% projected improvement in security incidents.

Inclusion and Accessibility

This KVI ensures that the vital signs monitoring solution can benefit different user groups, including elderly, people with disabilities, and low-income households. This KVI relates with MultiX goal to address digital inclusion and equity.

How to measure: Accessibility audits and feedback from vulnerable user groups. Affordability index (cost vs. average household income in target groups).

Target KVI: $\geq 90\%$ compliance according to feedback from vulnerable user groups; $\leq \text{€}20$ per month subscription.

Transparency and Explainability

This KVI measures how clearly the vital signs monitoring service operation, data use, and indications (e.g., why an alert was triggered) are communicated to end users. This KVI relates with MultiX goal to promote trust through explainable AI and interfaces.

How to measure: Percentage of users who understand how the service works (survey-based).

Target KVI: $\geq 85\%$ of users report they understand how the service works.

3.2.10 Specific MultiX features

This use case introduces multiple innovative aspects that go beyond current standardization efforts and related research projects:

- **Multi-static, multi-band, and multi-technology integration:** Unlike most existing use cases, which rely on a single technology or band, this use case leverages multiple RF bands (FR1/FR2, and potential FR3), combined with advanced MIMO systems and non-3GPP modalities (e.g., radar, LiDAR, cameras for validation), enabling high-resolution sensing and robustness.
- **Contact-free respiratory monitoring without wearables:** The system supports the passive detection of breathing patterns without requiring users to wear or interact with any device, thus improving comfort and usability for elderly or physically limited individuals.
- **Distributed sensing using static UEs and multiple antennas:** By integrating stationary UEs into the sensing mesh and coordinating distributed antennas, the system supports flexible deployments in typical residential environments.
- **Real-time fusion and intelligent perception:** The Data Access and Security Hub (DASH) and the MPS demonstrate real-time processing and interpretation of sensing data, enabling fast anomaly detection and alert generation.
- **Contribution to ISAC standardization:** The use case is supported by the MultiX project, which provides experimental validation across multiple testbeds and contributes requirements and lessons learned to standardization bodies (e.g., 3GPP, ETSI).

Specifically, the following key technical features innovate MultiX solutions:

- Robust detection of subtle movements in complex indoor environments

Sleep and sitting states involve extremely subtle motion, like chest displacement from breathing. Breathing and micromotion tracking depend on phase/frequency sensitivity and temporal coherence – even small estimation noise or pilot contamination can distort the inferred signal. The challenge lies in accurately isolating and detecting physiological micro-signals from cluttered, multi-reflection indoor channels.

- Calibration and drift in UE-to-AP (Access Point) channels

Over time, small changes in environment (e.g., phone position, blanket movement) may shift the propagation paths, affecting the CSI signature. This leads to calibration drift and false variation in breathing detection. Thus, the compensation is needed.

- Synchronization and clock offset between UE and sensing APs

While the UE transmits pilots, clock differences, propagation delays, or RF chain impairments can distort CSI phase and timing, which are essential for time of flight (ToF) / angle of arrival (AoA)-based localization or micromotion detection.

- Heterogeneous hardware integration across testbeds

MultiX involves multiple testbeds with differing RF frontends (e.g., massive MIMO, cell-free, USRP devices, commercial UEs). Integrating them into a coherent sensing setup with unified control and synchronization is non-trivial.

- End-to-End data pipeline stability and latency

From RF data capture to edge processing and remote monitoring, the testbed must maintain a reliable end-to-end pipeline under load – often with constrained compute and networking infrastructure.

3.2.11 Regulatory considerations

This section provides regulatory considerations in respect to GDPR [1], the Data Act [3] and the AI Act [4].

Table 9 presents the GDPR roles and responsibilities for this use case.

Table 9. GDPR Roles and Responsibilities in the Contact-free human localization and vital signs detection Use Case

Role	Who	Description
Data Subject	Monitored individuals (e.g., patients, elderly residents, home occupants)	Natural persons whose motion and vital signs are passively collected through sensing-enabled 6G and Wi-Fi devices
Data Controller	Healthcare provider / care organization / service operator	Entity that determines the purposes (e.g., health monitoring, alert generation) and means of processing personal data derived from contact-free sensing
Data Processor	Mobile Network Operator (MNO) / edge-cloud provider / AI analytics partner	Entities that process raw RF sensing data and fuse signals into health or localization results on behalf of the controller. Processing is done under a contract defining purpose limitation and data minimization

Table 10 shows the key aspects of the Data Act in relation with this use case.

Table 10. Key Aspects of the Data Act and Description in Relation to the Contact-free human localization and vital signs detection Use Case

Aspect	Description
Fair Access and Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Healthcare providers and patients must have fair access to processed and aggregated data outputs MNOs and infrastructure owners shall not restrict access to sensing data needed for interoperable e-health services
Data Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raw RF sensing data collected by MNOs may be shared with authorized analytics entities for edge processing and health anomaly detection Such sharing must follow transparent and proportionate data-use agreements as envisioned by the Data Act
Consumer Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitored individuals must be informed about what data is collected and how it is used They retain rights of access, rectification, erasure, and restriction of processing under GDPR
Business Protections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small AI analytics providers participating in the health-monitoring ecosystem shall be protected from dominant network operators imposing unfair contractual terms
Interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data exchange between MNOs, edge nodes, and healthcare applications must rely on common, open, and machine-readable formats to ensure portability and cross-vendor compliance

Table 11 provides the risk classification of the sensing data processing in this use case in relation with the AI Act.

Table 11. AI-Enabled Technologies in the Contact-free human localization and vital signs detection Use Case and their Risk Classification

Technology Enabled by AI	Risk Classification	Explanation
Sensing Data Processing	Limited Risk	Supports health monitoring but does not make automated decisions about individuals

3.3 Smart Home Virtual Security

3.3.1 Definition of the use case

A smart home is a house environment where devices, appliances and systems are interconnected through communication networks to provide automation, security, entertainment, energy efficiency, and other enhanced user experiences. Smart homes use Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, wireless communication, AI-driven automation, and cloud-based services to enable seamless interaction between users and their surroundings. Smart home ecosystems typically utilize Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, Zigbee, Z-Wave, and 3GPP communications to provide connectivity between devices such as smart switches, lighting systems, security cameras, motion sensors, door locks, voice assistants, and entertainment systems. The primary goal of a smart home is to improve convenience by automating routine tasks, optimizing energy consumption, and ensuring a safer living environment through real-time monitoring and control.

In this use case we concentrate on the security aspect of the smart home and, in particular, on the intruder detection ability, not only for the indoor part of the premises but also for the surrounding area of the house. By doing this, we exemplify how ISAC technology can create new business opportunities for telecom operators and other service providers allowing them to offer new services for the smart home sector.

The proposition is that a homeowner wishes to be informed of intruders wherever they may be, outside or inside their private property, that can be a person or a harmful animal, to ensure that residents at home feel comfortable and secure (Figure 4). Currently, this service is mainly achieved by utilizing IP/CCTV cameras, passive infrared sensors and microwave radars capable of monitoring and detecting objects and/or motion. However, these sensors require line-of-sight, their monitoring area capabilities are limited, and they can be easily accessed and damaged by malicious intruders. Wireless signals provided by 3GPP BSs, Wi-Fi CPE and UE with sensing capabilities make it possible to monitor wider areas without line-of-sight (LoS), with these devices being very hard or even impossible to be accessed and tampered with

by the intruders. In addition, the fusion of the sensing data of 3GPP and non-3GPP wireless devices can improve accuracy and ubiquity of the intruder detection service.

Figure 4. Smart home virtual security use case diagram

For the purposes of this use case, we consider a homeowner, Bob, who has been a subscriber to a certain telecom provider, called TELE. TELE informs Bob about a new security service, called SENSE, which can secure Bob's house with a virtual security system that does not require him to install any equipment or sensors to his premises. The new security system is able to protect both the interior and the surrounding area of Bob's house, without the installation of any equipment, since it is based on the new sensing capabilities provided by the wireless network (3GPP BSs, Wi-Fi CPEs and UEs), as shown in figure 1. With SENSE service Bob will receive tamper-proof sensing information from the outdoor base stations, covering the entire outdoor area with high accuracy and no blind spots. TELE will also upgrade the homeowner's Wi-Fi CPE and UEs with ones supporting sensing functionality, allowing them to receive high-accuracy sensing information also for the interior of the house, again with high accuracy and no blind spots. In this way, Bob will be notified of both outdoor and indoor intruders knowing their exact location.

3.3.2 Related use cases

Mapping to 3GPP and IEEE use cases

- 3GPP TR 22.837 [15].
- Use case of intruder detection in smart home [15].
- Performance requirements: Horizontal position accuracy (<10m), vertical position accuracy (<10 m), max sensing service latency (1000 ms), refreshing rate (<1 s), missed detection (<5%), false alarm (<2%).

- Use case of intruder detection in surroundings of smart home [15].
- Performance requirements: Horizontal position accuracy (<2m), max sensing service latency (1000 ms), refreshing rate (<1 s), missed detection (<0.1%), false alarm (<5%).

3.3.3 Example scenarios

Outdoor Intruder Detection

Outdoor intruder detection can be achieved by using 3GPP BSs to detect intruders within a surveillance area in the external perimeter of a home. Using ISAC technology, one or more BSs could detect movement and environmental changes, alerting homeowners or security personnel. Of course, this scenario can be extended so it can provide also non-human intrusion detection in the surveillance area of the home including animals, vehicles, UAVs, etc.

Indoor Intruder Detection

Indoor intruder detection can be achieved by using 3GPP UEs and Wi-Fi CPE with sensing ability to detect intruders within a home. Using ISAC technology, multiple small cells could detect movement and environmental changes, alerting homeowners or security personnel. This capability, similar to advanced home security systems, opens up new monetization opportunities for telco operators to offer security-focused services.

3.3.4 Preconditions

The outdoor surveillance area must be covered by at least one base station with sensing capabilities.

The indoor wireless equipment (3GPP UEs and Wi-Fi CPEs) must be able to sense the environment continuously.

The indoor wireless equipment must be placed in places inside the house, where their signal will not be blocked by large appliances, furniture, walls, etc.

3.3.5 Service flows

- Bob, the homeowner is a subscriber of telecom operator TELE who provides wireless services to Bob's property and the surrounding area. Outdoor coverage is provided by a 3GPP BS with sensing capabilities, while indoor coverage will be provided by a Wi-Fi CPE with sensing capabilities and one or more UEs also with sensing capabilities.
- The SENSE service is also able to support Bob's 3GPP and Wi-Fi wireless cameras (optional), both outside and inside the premises.
- Bob is able to designate the outdoor surveillance area, so whenever the sensing function of the BS detects an intruder within the indicated surveillance area, he will be notified via push notifications or SMS, so that he can decide on his next actions, that may include calling the police.
- In the case of indoor intruders, they can be detected by the sensing function of the Wi-Fi CPE and/or UEs.

- Due to the motion of an indoor human, the 3GPP signal measured by the UEs and the signal of the Wi-Fi CPE will be influenced.
- By analysing and collecting the sensing information, such as Doppler frequency shift, amplitude change and phase change, the behaviour of an indoor human could be detected. In such a case, Bob will again be notified and call the police.
- Similar services can also be provided by third party service providers who can obtain the necessary sensing data, after signing contracts with one or more telecom operators.

3.3.6 Postconditions

Due to the area-coverage, long- and short-distance sensing capability of the 3GPP base stations, 3GPP UEs and Wi-Fi CPEs the precision, efficiency and user friendliness of smart home security systems for intruder detection can be significantly improved. The network-based sensing can provide timely, continuous, accurate, and comprehensive sensing results, which can be utilised by telecom operators and security service providers.

3.3.7 Functional requirements

[FR3-1] The 6G network shall be able to configure and control sensing-enabled BSs, Wi-Fi CPEs and UEs.

[FR3-2] The 6G network shall provide a mechanism for an operator to authorize a UE for sensing.

[FR3-3] The 6G network shall be able to collect 3GPP and non-3GPP sensing-related information from sensing-enabled BSs, Wi-Fi CPEs and UEs.

[FR3-4] The 6G Network shall be able to decide whether 3GPP or non-3GPP sensing shall be performed.

[FR3-5] The 6G network shall be able to fuse 3GPP and non-3GPP sensing data.

[FR3-6] The 6G network shall be able to expose sensing data to one or more third party service providers.

3.3.8 Performance requirements

Table 12 shows the technical requirements for smart home virtual security use case.

Table 12. Performance requirements for Smart Home Virtual Security Use Case

KPI Name	Description	Target Value / Metric	Relevance to Use Case
Indoor Localization Accuracy	Accuracy of detecting human position indoors	≤ 0.5 m	Required for reliable indoor intruder detection

Outdoor Localization Accuracy	Accuracy of detecting human position outdoors	≤ 1 m	Required for reliable outdoor intruder detection
Max. detection Latency	Time from sensing intruder to alert generation	≤ 1 s	Ensures timely intervention during intruder detection
False Positive Alarm Rate	Rate of incorrectly triggered alerts	$\leq 2\%$	Ensures trust and reduces unnecessary alarm notifications
False Negative Alarm Rate	Rate of missed critical intrusion events	$\leq 1\%$	High reliability for intruder monitoring
Edge Processing Latency	Time required by MPS/DASH to process and fuse sensor data	≤ 100 ms	Supports real-time responsiveness and scalability
Energy Consumption (UE standby)	Power used by static UE during passive monitoring	$\leq 5\%$ daily battery drain	Ensures long-term usability for static UE scenarios
Refreshing Rate	Rate of the sensing refreshing over monitoring periods	≤ 1 s	Ensures monitoring continuity

3.3.9 KVs and KVIs

User Acceptance and Perceived Trustworthiness

This KVI measures how willing end users are to adopt the proposed virtual security solution, and whether they trust its operation and purpose. This KVI relates with MultiX goal to demonstrate a user-centric wireless sensing solution.

How to measure: End-user surveys or focus groups before and after pilot deployment.

Target KVI: $\geq 80\%$ of surveyed users express trust and willingness to adopt.

Perceived and Real Privacy Preservation

This KVI evaluates both the actual protection of personal data (e.g., no identifiable information collected) and how users perceive their privacy is protected. This KVI relates with MultiX goal to ensure the provision of GDPR-compliant and ethically aligned sensing services.

How to measure: User feedback on perceived data exposure.

Target KVI: 100% GDPR and ethics compliance; $\leq 10\%$ of users raise privacy concerns post-demonstration.

Non-intrusiveness

This KVI measures how seamlessly the system operates in the background without requiring cameras, active sensors, or any action required by the user. This KVI relates with MultiX goal to develop non-invasive sensing methods using existing infrastructure.

How to measure: User rating of intrusiveness (e.g., 1-5 scale).

Target KVI: $\leq 2/5$ average intrusiveness rating.

Contribution to Public Safety and Wellbeing

This KVI assesses the broader impact of the proposed smart home virtual security service on community safety, perceived security, and quality of life. This KVI relates with MultiX goal to improve real-time situational awareness for safety.

How to measure: Before/after statistics on security incidents in pilot areas. Feedback from local authorities or citizen associations.

Target KVI: 20–30% projected improvement in security incidents.

Inclusion and Accessibility

This KVI ensures that the smart home virtual security solution can benefit different user groups, including elderly, people with disabilities, and low-income households. This KVI relates with MultiX goal to address digital inclusion and equity.

How to measure: Accessibility audits and feedback from vulnerable user groups. Affordability index (cost vs. average household income in target groups).

Target KVI: $\geq 90\%$ compliance according to feedback from vulnerable user groups; $\leq \text{€}20$ per month subscription.

Transparency and Explainability

This KVI measures how clearly the smart home virtual security service operation, data use, and indications (e.g., why an alert was triggered) are communicated to end users. This KVI relates with MultiX goal to promote trust through explainable AI and interfaces.

How to measure: Percentage of users who understand how the service works (survey-based).

Target KVI: $\geq 85\%$ of users report they understand how the service works.

3.3.10 Specific MultiX features

Today smart home solutions in general face several technical challenges due to the variety of sensors and their communication technologies that are utilised within the home environment. Current smart home solutions utilise a mixture of Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, Zigbee, Z-Wave, and other wired or wireless sensors, which most of the times require specific gateways for their interconnection. This makes their installation and use quite complex for everyday users. Many

smart home setups even require manual configuration and separate cloud accounts. In addition, most of these devices are easily accessible to intruders and they can be easily damaged and become unfunctional.

MultiX may overcome these technical challenges by providing a seamless, plug-and-play solution that eliminates the use of any sensor installation, the need for multiple gateways, specialized routers, and complex manual configurations. Unlike traditional smart home ecosystems that rely on separate hubs for Wi-Fi Bluetooth, Zigbee, Z-Wave and other communications protocols, MultiX integrates multi-sensor multi-band and multi-technology capabilities directly into the 6G-RAN architecture. The MP6RC acts as an intelligent RAN orchestrator. Additionally, the DASH provides a unified platform for secure data processing storage and privacy management. Most importantly, MultiX introduces a plug-and-play framework that makes smart home adoption more accessible, reliable, and future-proof for everyday users.

3.3.11 Regulatory considerations

This section provides regulatory considerations in respect to GDPR [1], the Data Act [3] and the AI Act [4].

Table 13 presents the GDPR roles and responsibilities for this use case.

Table 13. GDPR Roles and Responsibilities in the Smart Home Virtual Security Use Case

Role	Who	Description
Data Subject	Individuals inside and outside the house	These are the intruders whose location and movement data are collected through sensing-enabled 6G and Wi-Fi devices while they move inside and outside the house
Data Controller	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MNO Third party 	Depending on who provides the service these entities are processing personal data for the sensing-based analytics service. Each one defines part of the processing chain – e.g., the MNO handles sensing and fusion of network data, while the third party determines how the results are aggregated and interpreted
Data Processor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MNO Third party 	Depending on contractual arrangements these entities may also act as processors for one another – e.g., a third party might

		process fused data on behalf of the MNO, or vice versa
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Table 14 shows the key aspects of the Data Act in relation with this use case.

Table 14. Key Aspects of the Data Act and Description in Relation to the Smart Home Virtual Security Use Case

Aspect	Description
Fair Access and Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The MNO who operates the 6G and Wi-Fi infrastructure must not unreasonably restrict or monopolize access to the data that results from intruders' movements inside and outside the house A third-party, shall be able to obtain that data from the MNO through transparent and fair-use contracts, ensuring that the terms are not abusive toward smaller service providers
Data Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The MNO collects raw 6G and Wi-Fi sensing data (radio reflections, device presence, positioning) and processes these data A third party may also process these data to provide a security service Sharing therefore takes place between network operators (data holders) and third parties (data user) – a core scenario envisioned by the Data Act
Consumer Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intruders (individuals) generate data through their movement and presence inside and outside the house, captured by 6G and Wi-Fi sensing systems operated by the MNOs
Business Protections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Third parties, being smaller analytics companies, must be protected from dominant telecom operators dictating unfair commercial conditions
Interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6G network operators and a third-party analytics provider must exchange sensing data through common, open, and machine-readable formats The fusion of 6G and Wi-Fi sensing data must follow shared technical standards so that any authorized actor can participate

Table 15 provides the risk classification of the sensing data processing in this use case in relation with the AI Act.

Table 15. AI-Enabled Technologies in the Smart Home Virtual Security Use Case and their Risk Classification

Technology Enabled by AI	Risk Classification	Explanation
Sensing Data Processing	Limited Risk	The sensing data provide insights into human presence information and movement patterns within the house and its immediate vicinity, which pose a limited risk to home intruders and to society and to society in general

3.4 Low-altitude UAV management

3.4.1 Definition of the use case

With advancements in UAV technology, lightweight and compact civilian UAVs have become increasingly valuable in areas such as aerial imaging, agriculture, and cartography. The commercial use of UAVs is rapidly expanding, bringing these applications closer to everyday reality. Operating primarily at low altitudes, these UAVs introduce several safety and regulatory challenges, including unauthorized airspace entry and potential mid-air collisions.

In certain scenarios, UAVs adhere to meticulously designed flight plans to ensure safe, efficient, and compliant operations within designated airspace. Tasks such as parcel delivery, surveillance, and environmental assessment rely on predefined routes that control the UAVs' altitude, speed, and direction. For example, a delivery UAV travels directly from the dispatch center to the recipient, while one used for environmental monitoring navigates from its base to a specific observation zone. Designing and optimizing these routes is essential for maintaining operational safety and efficiency. These paths, approved by UAV operators, are crafted to minimize travel distance, avoid no-fly zones, and maintain safe separation from obstacles like buildings, vegetation, and other UAVs. Strict adherence to these routes reduces accident risks and boosts service reliability.

Despite being equipped with sensors for real-time navigation, UAVs can experience performance degradation due to environmental factors such as lighting conditions, weather, or terrain features. These limitations can affect the UAVs' ability to accurately assess their position, altitude, or speed, potentially causing deviations from their planned routes. In densely operated areas, such as those used for delivery services, sensor inaccuracies can increase the likelihood of UAV collisions, posing significant safety concerns.

Current UAV tracking solutions, including ground-based radar and specialized monitoring systems, offer route surveillance capabilities. However, their widespread implementation is

hindered by high setup and maintenance expenses, as well as the scarcity of suitable installation locations.

3.4.2 Related use cases

From 3GPP TR 22.837 [15]

- Use case on UAV flight trajectory tracing. Outdoor. Positioning accuracy 1-2 m (horizontal and vertical). Velocity accuracy 1-2 m/s (horizontal and vertical). Sensing resolution 1m x 1m ~10m x 10m (same for velocity). Max sensing service latency 100~1000 ms.
- Use case on network-assisted sensing to avoid UAV collision. Outdoor. Positioning accuracy 1m (horizontal and vertical). Velocity accuracy 1 m/s (horizontal and vertical). Sensing resolution 1m x 1m ~10m x 10m (same for velocity). Max sensing service latency 500ms. Refreshing rate 0.5 s. Missed detection N/A. False alarm N/A.
- Use case on sensing for UAV intrusion detection. Outdoor. Confidence 95%. Positioning accuracy ≤ 5 m (horizontal and vertical). Velocity accuracy N/A (horizontal and vertical). Sensing resolution 10 (velocity 5). Max sensing service latency ≤ 1000 ms. Refreshing rate ≤ 1 s. Missed detection $\leq 5\%$. False alarm $\leq 5\%$.

From 5G-ACIA project [18]

- Use case on detection and tracking of ground and aerial vehicles: leveraging ISAC capabilities in cellular networks offers a highly effective solution to the challenges posed by UAV operations in industrial environments. ISAC enables continuous, real-time tracking of UAVs without requiring them to broadcast active beacon signals, significantly enhancing situational awareness. This capability strengthens safety by supporting dynamic flight-path adjustments and advanced collision-avoidance mechanisms, ensuring that UAVs can operate safely even in complex or congested areas. Beyond controlled UAV operations, ISAC's advanced sensing functions also enable the reliable detection of unauthorized or non-cooperative drones. This allows for rapid and appropriate responses to potential security breaches, protecting sensitive industrial zones from aerial intrusions. By unifying communication and sensing into a single framework, ISAC ensures consistent monitoring performance and robust operational continuity.

3.4.3 Example scenarios

Low-altitude UAV management

6G network could provide sensing service by collecting sensing data, transmitting, processing and storing sensing data, as well as supporting sensing result exposure to third application platforms. Facing these new data characteristics, the 6G network capability of data processing needs to be extended from 5G network including multi-source heterogeneous data collection, efficient and guaranteed large-scale data transmission, efficient data processing within the

network, and unified data storage to support multi-node cooperative sensing and multi-node information convergence.

Upon request, the 6G network operator is expected to provide UAV flight trajectory tracking services to trusted third-party applications, such as UAV service operators, regulatory agencies, Uncrewed Aerial System Traffic Management (UTM) systems, UAV itself, etc.

In the low-altitude UAV supervision scenario, shown visually in Figure 5, the 6G network could be used for sensing the UAV intrusion such as a UAV illegally flying in a restricted area, including government and company regions. In this scenario, the network security and data security need to be guaranteed due to the privacy issue. Furthermore, the historical data may be used to identify an illegal UAV. In addition to the communication property of the detected UAV itself, the data management in this low-altitude sensing scenario must be operated within the network.

Figure 5. Low-altitude UAV management use case diagram

3.4.4 Preconditions

In this use case, an UTM system provides package delivery services within an area covered by a 6G network.

Network operator NN provides 6G sensing service for UAV flight assistance service, including: illegal UAV intrusion, UAV flight trajectory tracing, UAV collision prediction, etc. NN is MultiX-capable and can make use of wireless base stations to sense the airspace within their coverage area and report the sensing information (including tracked UAV and the environment around the UAV) to the UTM.

Company MM uses the UTM to supervise the low-altitude UAVs and manage potential illegal intrusion into the restricted areas. MM has proved its restricted area information to the UTM.

The UTM provides specific details to the 6G network operator NN, including the characteristics of the UAV that will be tracked, along with details about the time and location for flight tracing. This information includes regulated flight paths as well as potential areas where the UAV might temporarily deviate from its route.

The 6G network operator NN can realize 6G data collection, transmission, processing and storage within the network, providing sensing results to the UTM.

3.4.5 Service flows

1. When the scheduled time for tracking begins, the 6G network operator activates the UAV trajectory tracing service within the designated area until the tracking session ends. The UTM then launches UAV#1, which takes off from the delivery source and heads toward the destination, following a pre-set flight path.
 - Using radio sensing, the MPS of MultiX detects UAV#1 and continuously gathers data on its position and movement, such as distance, velocity and angle from a base station. These metrics, also known as 3GPP sensing data, are sent to the MP6R Controller.
2. During the flight, if UAV#1 leaves the coverage range of one base station and enters a new coverage zone, the MP6R controller could let the old base station stop radio sensing, and switch to new base station for sensing UAV#1 until it is out of coverage. This transition is based on the UAV's estimated position and velocity.
3. The MP6R can aggregates sensing data from multiple sources to estimate UAV#1's location and velocity. A similar approach can also be applied to UAV#2 - UAV#N, in the case there are multiple UAVs providing service in the area. This real-time information is then transmitted to UTM, which monitors the UAV's trajectory.
4. If UAV#1 - UAV#N deviate from prescribed routes, the UTM receives alerts, allowing them to take corrective action and redirect the UAVs as necessary.

3.4.6 Postconditions

UAV#1 has followed the tracked flight route.

3.4.7 Functional requirements

[FR4-1] The network operator shall be able to collect sensing-related data.

[FR4-2] The network operator shall be able to expose sensing results to one or more third-party service providers.

3.4.8 Performance requirements

Table 16 shows the technical requirements defined for this use case.

Table 16. Low-altitude UAV management Use Case performance requirements

KPI Name	Description	Target Value / Metric	Relevance to Use Case
Outdoor positioning	Accuracy of detecting drone position	≤ 1 m	Required for accurate drone tracking
Outdoor velocity	Accuracy of detecting drone velocity	≤ 1 m/s	Required for accurate drone tracking
Sensing resolution – Range resolution	The smallest difference in range that the system can detect	≤ 1 m	Required for accurate drone tracking
Sensing resolution – Velocity resolution	The smallest difference in velocity that the system can detect	≤ 1 m/s	Required for accurate drone tracking
Max. sensing service latency	Time from triggering the sensing service to the sensing information is exposed	≤ 0.1 s	Ensures almost real-time operability
Refreshing rate	The rate at which the sensing result is generated	0.05 s – 1 s	Ensures almost real-time operability
False Alarm	The rate of detecting a drone when it is not present	$\leq 2\%$	Ensures reliability
Missed detection	The rate of not detecting a drone when it is present	$\leq 2\%$	Ensures reliability

3.4.9 KVs and KVIs

Economical inclusion

Currently, regular delivery services have a high cost due to several factors, including the purchase and maintenance of vans, gasoline, salaries, and other expenses. Hence, the shipping typically is a high extra charge over the product. On the other hand, a MultiX-based delivery service will considerably reduce its cost since drones are much cheaper, and their maintenance is also more economical. Hence, the price for the end user will be significantly lower and therefore much more economically accessible.

How to measure: Ask for feedback or conduct surveys to evaluate the reduction in the price of the MultiX-based service compared with the traditional van-based service.

Target KVI: any reduction of cost from current prices.

Operational cost savings

MultiX can be used for drone delivery over a standalone 6G infrastructure without any specialized hardware. In addition, MultiX can provide the optimal route without any risk of crashing, hence it saves energy and equipment. Drones are much lighter than vans and they require less transportation energy. All in all, it provides a more sustainable delivery service.

How to measure: How much money can be saved compared to a traditional delivery service.

Target KVI: the amount saved would be the opportunity cost of applying MultiX system.

Environmental sustainability

If drone delivery is deployed at scale, MultiX would become part of a more electrified ecosystem of drone fleet that helps reduce CO₂ emissions and lower energy consumption per operation, directly contributing to greater ecological efficiency.

How to measure: how many tons of CO₂ are emitted per operation compared to the current system.

Target KVI: a specific amount of reduction in polluting gas emissions.

3.4.10 Specific MultiX features

Safe UAV tracking and navigation pose some technical challenges that MultiX mitigates.

1. UAVs can have a velocity up to 120 km/h. This high velocity distorts the radio-frequency signal by adding a Doppler frequency shift, which causes carrier frequency offset. Therefore, the chances of demodulating the signal reduce significantly. The MPS of MultiX supports Orthogonal Time Frequency Space (OTFS) that modulates the information in the Delay-Doppler domain rather than in the time-frequency domain (as OFDM does). Hence, OTFS is suitable for high-Doppler ISAC applications.
2. Together with the 6G communication transceiver, the UAVs generally have on board different types of sensors to assist the navigation. These sensors can help the UAV to get physical awareness and the information from these sensors can be exposed to the MultiX solution by the DASH.
3. If many UAVs are flying, it is imperative to coordinate the trajectories of all the UAVs to avoid collision. To this end, the system requires a centralized entity to coordinate the different UAVs. The MultiX MP6RC controller not only manages mobility but also coordinates sensing and communication across the different RANs.

3.4.11 Regulatory considerations

This section provides regulatory considerations in respect to GDPR [1], the Data Act [3] and the AI Act [4].

Table 17 presents the GDPR roles and responsibilities for this use case.

Table 17. GDPR Roles and Responsibilities in the Low-altitude UAV management Use Case

Role	Who	Description
Data Subject	UAV operators or individuals	Individuals whose personal data may be indirectly collected through UAV tracking (e.g., if UAVs capture location or visual data)
Data Controller	UAV operator and MNO	Entities responsible for collecting, storing, and managing UAV sensing and positioning data
Data Processor	MNO or third-party analytics provider	Entities that process data on behalf of the controller, which may include the MNO or third-party service providers

Table 18 shows the key aspects of the Data Act in relation with this use case.

Table 18. Key Aspects of the Data Act and Description in Relation to the Low-altitude UAV management Use Case

Aspect	Description
Fair Access and Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MNO must provide non-discriminatory access to UAV sensing and positioning data for service providers a third-party analytics provider, shall be able to obtain that data from the MNOs through transparent and fair-use contracts
Data Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MNO collects sensing data MNO or third-party service provider processes this data into UAVs positioning and trajectories Data is exchanged between network operators, public authorities and third-party entities under transparent, fair-use contracts ensuring proportional rights and obligations
Consumer Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UAV operators generate data through deploying UAVs, captured by 6G sensing systems operated by MNO UAV operators must be informed about how their operational data is used and shared
Business Protections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UAV operator must be able to access aggregated sensing data without being locked into an exclusive contract with any MNO

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any third-party analytics provider must be protected from dominant operators abusing their position by imposing unfair commercial conditions
Interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6G network operator, the third-party analytics provider, and UAV operators must exchange sensing data through common, open, and machine-readable formats

Table 19 provides the risk classification of the sensing data processing in this use case in relation with the AI Act.

Table 19. AI-Enabled Technologies in the Low-altitude UAV management Use Case and their Risk Classification

Technology Enabled by AI	Risk Classification	Explanation
Sensing Data Processing	High risk	Considered high risk because it contributes to safety-critical decisions (airspace management)

3.5 Gesture Recognition in Industrial Environments

The use case “Gesture Recognition in Industrial Environments” was developed in 5G-ACIA and described in detail in the 5G-ACIA whitepaper on ISAC use cases and requirements [18]. This section is based on the original description from 5G-ACIA, which is updated and enhanced towards the MultiX objectives.

Furthermore, gesture recognition also provides benefits in other areas than industrial environments, for instance, in healthcare and for caring professionals.

3.5.1 Description of the use case

Interaction of robots and humans in factory environments is a dynamically evolving aspect of modern manufacturing. This collaboration involves various levels of cooperation, communication, and coordination between robotic systems and human operators.

Cobots (collaborative robots) are designed to directly and collaboratively interact with humans, often in close proximity. Efficient interaction ensures that cobots and humans can work together seamlessly, leveraging each other’s strengths to maximize the overall productivity of manufacturing processes.

Cobots include interactive modes. With cobots, easy, continual, and intuitive interaction is of the utmost relevance. (Touch) panels and other handheld devices for interacting with robots are impractical in some environments and scenarios, for example, if a worker is wearing heavy protective gloves or needs his hands to perform a concurrent task. In other scenarios, for example, when performing certain dangerous tasks, nonstop visual monitoring of the cobot by the human is required. Factory environments can also be too noisy to use a voice interface.

In such scenarios, it would be helpful to have an easy and intuitive way of interacting, for example with gestures. This can be described as a touchless interface. Two main functions are required for reading gestures: object detection and pattern recognition. In contrast to continuous gesture recognition (for example, by moving a mouse pointer on a screen), discrete gesture detection is more appropriate for scenarios involving interactions with a cobot. Typically, a predefined set of gestures is employed, with each of them corresponding to a specific action. Interactions can be additionally enhanced by visual acknowledgements or other methods to assist communication between humans and cobots.

Gesture-based interfaces are likely to become more sophisticated and permit the use of a wider range of gestures for more nuanced communication between humans and cobots. Human gestures can be categorized as follows:

- Hand and arm gestures: hand gestures, arm positions and movements, finger positions and pointing directions
- Body and limb gestures: full body actions, motions or poses
- Head gestures: nodding, shaking or pointing with the head
- Facial gestures: winking or closing one or both eyes

When cobots work alongside humans, it must be prevented that incorrectly used gesture commands provoke dangerous situations.

The performance requirements for sensing objects and detecting gesture patterns can vary depending on the set of gestures and the scenario.

3.5.2 Related use cases

5G-ACIA

The use case “Gesture Recognition in Industrial Environments” was developed in 5G-ACIA [18]. It contains functional requirements and KPIs for monitoring and recognition of hand, facial, head, and body gestures.

3GPP TR 22.837 “Feasibility Study on Integrated Sensing and Communication” [15]

Use case “Coarse Gesture Recognition for Application Navigation and Immersive Interaction” and “Roaming for Sensing Service of Sports Monitoring” in 3GPP TR 22.837 [15] use recognition of human body gestures for monitoring of correct positions during sport exercises and hand gestures for touchless control and Immersive XR applications.

IEEE P802.11bf WLAN Sensing

Several use cases and scenarios with gesture recognition are described with corresponding requirements in [19]. They include home appliance control in room sensing. Gesture recognition is categorized at different ranges: short range – finger movements, medium range – hand movements, large range – full body movements.

Hexa-X project

The Hexa-X project describes gesture recognition for human-machine interfaces as part of the use case family “Immersive telepresence for enhanced interactions” in a corresponding deliverable [9].

ETSI ISG Terahertz

The ETSI Industry Specification Group (ISG) Terahertz (THz) released a report [20] containing use case for THz-based sensing for precise characterization of teacher’s motions and gestures in remote education and for capturing movements and gestures in interactive immersive XR.

3GPP TR 22.870 “Study on 6G Use Cases and Service Requirements” [21]

MultiX has provided its use case “Gesture Recognition in Industrial Environments” to the 3GPP SA1 study on 6G use cases and requirements through contributions S1-253315 / S1-253649 and S1-254246 / S1-254396. It is part of the clause on integrated sensing and communication in 3GPP TR 22.870 [21].

3.5.3 Example scenarios

Source: 5G-ACIA / ZVEI e. V.

Figure 6. ISAC for gesture recognition in an industrial environment [18]

Figure 6 shows an example scenario for gesture recognition in industrial environments. Here, the movement of an AMR is controlled by specific body and hand gestures such as gestures for commands :Follow (body gesture) or :Stop (hand gesture).

3.5.4 Preconditions

A mobile network with ISAC capabilities and wireless coverage is available in the relevant areas of the factory. Standardized interfaces are used for accessing information including detailed estimates of the margin of error of the provided measurement data.

3.5.5 Service Flows

- Step 1: A worker wishing to take an AMR with integrated UE somewhere else to perform a task walks toward it and stands in front of it.
- Step 2: The worker laterally raises his/her arms, which is a predefined gesture for telling the robot to follow.
- Step 3: Specialized radio signals from the infrastructure and/or nearby UEs are used to sense the environment and the gestures.
- Step 4: The sensor data is processed and the gesture is interpreted.
- Step 5: The recognized request is forwarded to the AMR.
- Step 6: The AMR follows the worker while the system continually interprets any new gestures.

3.5.6 Postconditions

The worker has used gesture detection to deliberately control a nearby machine. This is done without the need to touch the machine or use a device to issue commands. This increases the worker's efficiency and productivity.

3.5.7 Functional requirements

For recognizing relevant body language in industrial environments, the ISAC system is required to have the following abilities:

[FR5-1] Monitoring and recognition of a worker's hand gestures.

[FR5-2] Monitoring and recognition of a worker's limb positions.

[FR5-3] Monitoring and recognition of a worker's body positions.

[FR5-4] Monitoring and recognition of a worker's head gestures.

[FR5-5] Monitoring and recognition of a worker's facial expressions.

3.5.8 Performance requirements

The sensing resolution is proportional to the accuracy of recognition. The following KPI values have been calculated for currently available camera-based recognition systems. No angular resolution for the sensor is given, since it depends on the distance from the subject. A combination of different sensors could be implemented to meet these requirements.

The technical performance requirements (shown in Table 20) assume an indoor sensing service area. Neither horizontal nor vertical velocity resolution is applicable for this use case of gesture recognition.

Table 20. Performance Requirements for ISAC for gesture recognition in industrial environments Use Case

Scenario	Confidence level	Sensing resolution (h)orizontal (v)ertical	Max sensing latency	Refresh rate	Missed detection	False alarm
Hand gestures	99 %	h,v: ≤ 0.02 m	≤ 20 ms	≤ 0.02 s	≤ 1 %	≤ 10 %

Body and limb gestures	99 %	h,v: ≤ 0.1 m	≤ 20 ms	≤ 0.02 s	≤ 1 %	≤ 10 %
Head gestures	99 %	h,v: ≤ 0.05 m	≤ 20 ms	≤ 0.02 s	≤ 1 %	≤ 10 %
Facial gestures	99 %	h,v: ≤ 0.002 m	≤ 20 ms	≤ 0.02 s	≤ 1 %	≤ 10 %

Sensing resolution of hand gestures has been derived from [22] and [23]. Sensing resolution of body and limb gestures has been derived from [24] and [25]. Sensing resolution of head and facial gestures has been derived from [26].

Source of the original table of performance requirements of ISAC for gesture recognition in industrial environments is [18].

3.5.9 Specific MultiX features

The sensing capabilities for the different types of gestures are integrated in the MPS. This allows a high-quality recognition and identification of the gestures that are controlling autonomous mobile robots. Furthermore, the MPS provides necessary functionality such as authorization of human actors providing gestures as commands to AMRs.

This use case is only provided as an important use case for a Multi-sensorial MultiX Perception System. The use case “Gesture Recognition in Industrial Environments” will not be implemented in a MultiX PoC.

3.5.10 Regulatory considerations

This section provides regulatory considerations in respect to GDPR [1], the Data Act [3] and the AI Act [4].

Table 21 presents the GDPR roles and responsibilities for this use case.

Table 21. GDPR Roles and Responsibilities in the Gesture Recognition in Industrial Environments Use Case

Role	Who	Description
Data Subject	Worker providing gestures to AMR	The gestures of the worker are recognized to translate them into commands for the AMR. This may include gestures such as facial gestures which can be considered personal data
Data Controller	Factory owner, AMR developer	AMR developer provides the means to use gesture recognition for controlling AMRs, the factory owner decides to use gesture recognition as a touchless input method

Data Processor	Operator of the private industrial communication network, Perception system for interpretation of gestures	The sensing data is generated and transmitted in the communication system to the perception system, which process the sensing data to recognize the gestures for controlling the AMR. The perception system also must ensure the authorization of the human provider of the gestures
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Table 22 shows the key aspects of the Data Act in relation with this use case.

Table 22. Key Aspects of the Data Act and Description in Relation to the Gesture Recognition in Industrial Environments Use Case

Aspect	Description
Fair Access and Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensing data of gestures is related to factory processes • Use by involved individuals for personal (non-business) purposes is not foreseen
Data Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensing data of gestures is related to factory processes and to specific situations. Sharing with public sector is not foreseen
Consumer Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Devices belong to the factory, which can access data generated by them for gesture recognition • Access is usually limited the execution of production tasks and to cases where logs need to be consulted (e.g. for root cause investigations)
Business Protections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensing data of gestures in factory internal data • No data sharing with others anticipated • Relevant if identification of gestures is performed by external service providers
Interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Globally harmonized gestures for non-confusing control of AMR of different international vendors

Table 23 provides the risk classification of the sensing data processing in this use case in relation with the AI Act.

Table 23. AI-Enabled Technologies in the Gesture Recognition in Industrial Environments Use Case and their Risk Classification

Technology Enabled by AI	Risk Classification	Explanation
Sensing Data Processing	Limited (potential for High / Unacceptable)	Only gestures are recognized, not complete emotions or characteristics that can identify a person. However, gesture recognition, especially recognition of facial gestures, might be extended to recognition of specific persons or facial recognition

3.6 Smart Shopping Tracker

3.6.1 Definition of the use case

The indoor location analytics is expected to see exponential growth from \$14.09 billion in 2024 to \$41.66 billion in 2029 at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 24.2%. The growth in the forecast period can be attributed to initiatives for smart cities, inefficiency of the GPS technology in indoor premises, demand for navigation, growing need for accurate and real-time location services and increasing adoption of data analytics in the retail sector [27]. Furthermore, the World Economic Forum published a report on the Top 10 emerging technologies with “collaborative sensing” as one of them, outlining the opportunity for ISAC to “combine distributed sensors [...] to improve decision making, urban systems and autonomous technologies”.

3.6.2 Related Use Cases

Other similar and applicable examples of smart shopping tracker are:

3GPP SA1

- TR 22.870; Study on 6G Use Cases and Service Requirements; Release 20 [21]:
 - Use case about enabling non-3GPP wireless sensing.

IEEE 802.11bf

- 11-20/1712r2; TGbf Use Cases document [28]:
 - Use case about room sensing.
 - Use case about store sensing.

3.6.3 Example scenarios

The described use case here demonstrates the business opportunities of ISAC enabled indoor analytics for MNOs and service providers to offer novel services to the retail sector. The proposition is that a shop owner in a larger shopping mall is interested in knowing which products customers are checking out most in their store. The store owner then finds out about a new service a company called SENSOR - not affiliated with the shopping mall or with any particular MNO - offers to retailers, allowing them to learn which parts of their store (and products displayed in that are a) customers are most interested in. This is conveyed as a 3D representation of the store's interior and a heatmap-like overlay showing the customer interest. Another important benefit of sensing by 6G is the fact that risk of personal privacy being compromised is much less compared to camera-based sensing approaches.

The scenario is shown in Figure 7 and illustrates SENSOR (third-party service provider), the store owner and two MNOs, MNO A and MNO B. Furthermore, the store (shown on the bottom left) rents a broadband connection from MNO A which is operational inside the store. Inside the store are users with 6G UEs from MNO A and MNO B and all devices are 6G and Wi-Fi sensing capable.

Figure 7. Smart Shopping Tracker scenario utilising sensing results from multiple MNOs

3.6.4 Preconditions

SENSOR has contracts with multiple MNOs, and it is assumed that both MNO A and MNO B have 6G coverage of the shopping mall and have sensing capabilities in their 6G networks. Furthermore, the store owner also bought a broadband package from MNO A that comes with a sensing-enabled Wi-Fi AP and offers general internet access to all staff at the store. This Wi-Fi sensing station is under MNO A control.

As illustrated in Figure 7, both MNOs have an AF (Application Function) deployed in their network offering a Wi-Fi sensing enablement via an application on all 6G UEs.

UE1 and UE2 are registered with MNO A and UE3 is registered with MNO B. All three UEs are 6G and Wi-Fi sensing-enabled and have also registered with the AF of their operator.

Users UE1, UE2, and UE3 have explicitly opted for being part of the sensing operations offered by their respective MNOs. This consent allows them to control when and where they can be part of a sensing operation, possibly in exchange for potential incentives.

The shop owner receives SENSOR services with information about which products were of most interest to their customers. Once the shop owner completed their sign-up process with SENSOR and booked a sensing service, SENSOR issues a sensing service request to MNO A and B providing the necessary information about the target sensing service area (e.g. cartesian coordinates of the shop outline), the desired sensing result KPIs for the sensing results, and the daily opening times of the store when sensing results shall be provided.

3.6.5 Service Flows

At the opening time of store's business days, both MNOs start setting up their sensing activities to provide the sensing results SENSOR requested, executing the following service flows:

- Using the provided location (i.e. TSSA (Time-Synchronized Spatial Analysis)) of the store, both MNO start continuously checking for available sensing entities (TRPs and UEs) in the TSSA for sensing operations.
- MNO A identifies UE1 and UE2 to be in proximity of the store and MNO B identifies UE3.
- Both MNOs start performing sensing operations with the identified UEs and sensing data is sent to the MNO's CN (Core Network) for processing into sensing results for potential exposure to SENSOR.
- While continuously assessing the KPIs of the generated sensing results (e.g. target object identification confidence level, resolution accuracy), both MNOs' networks determine that the sensing result KPIs have not been met and consults their AF for assistance information to utilise Wi-Fi sensing of all three UEs located inside the TSSA.
- The AF of each MNO reaches out to the registered UEs that are capable of performing Wi-Fi sensing to provide sensing data using Wi-Fi APs that are discoverable by UEs.
- As UE1 and UE2 are with MNO A and the store's AP is from the same MNO, the AF of MNO A assists MNO A's CN to perform Wi-Fi sensing.
- MNO A uses the Wi-Fi sensing data and fuses it with the 6G sensing data to process them into sensing results and expose them to SENSOR.

3.6.6 Postconditions

MNO A can successfully provide sensing results that meet the requested KPIs through 6G and Wi-Fi sensing data fusion resulting in SENSOR being able to offer their service to the store's owner (i.e. generate a heatmap of customer interest overlaid onto a 3D representation of store interior).

The store owner can access the third-party service provider's website through a browser and app at any point in time and check out in which aisle and shelve customers spent most of their time in the store.

3.6.7 Functional requirements

[FR6-1] 6G Network shall be able to collect sensing-related capabilities from 6G UEs with sensing-enabled Wi-Fi STA (station) functionalities.

[FR6-2] 6G Network shall be able to configure 6G UEs with sensing-enabled Wi-Fi STA functionalities to perform sensing.

[FR6-3] 6G Network shall be able to decide whether 6G or non-6G sensing shall be performed.

[FR6-4] 6G Network shall be able to switch between 6G and non-6G sensing while executing a sensing activity.

[FR6-5] 6G Network shall be able to fuse 6G and non-6G sensing data into sensing results.

[FR6-6] 6G Network shall be able to expose sensing results to one or more third party service providers.

3.6.8 Performance requirements

The technical requirements for the smart shopping tracker are shown in Table 24.

Table 24. Performance requirements for smart shopping tracker Use Case

Scenario	Sensing service area	Confidence level [%]	Accuracy of positioning estimate by sensing (for a target confidence level) (note 3)		Accuracy of velocity estimate by sensing (for a target confidence level)		Sensing resolution		Fine Motion [m]	Refreshing rate [s]	Missed detection [%] (note 1)	False alarm [%] (note 1)
			Horizontal [m]	Vertical [m]	Horizontal [m/s]	Vertical [m/s]	Range resolution [m]	Velocity resolution (horizontal / vertical) [m/s x m/s]				
Smart Shopping Tracker	Indoor	95	[1.0]	[1.0]	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	[0.3]	n/a	n/a	n/a

3.6.9 KVs and KVIs

The 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) set out by the United Nations [29] are used as a framework to describe the societal key value of the smart shopping tracker use case to the wider society.

With regards to the “Decent Work and Economic Growth” SDG, the sensing results shared by SENSOR may allow store owners to re-assess the density of individuals in their stores for improved health and safety measures. Based on SENSOR’s offerings, stores can better organise their product lines and product presentations, leading to an increase in customer satisfaction potentially resulting in an increased annual turnover of the store. This will contribute to a sustained economic growth of this SDG especially for least developed

countries. With regards to the SDG on “Reduced Inequalities”, the shop owner may request to learn how many handicapped individuals shop in their store and which products they are most interested in or which areas of the shop they are not accessing at all. This may lead to a re-organisation of the store for equal access.

With regards to the SDG on “Responsible Consumption and Production”, the insights from SENSOR’s provided insights in shopping behaviour of visitors to the store will eventually indicate whether certain product ranges or brands are not of interest to individuals. These insights allow store owners to re-plan their offerings resulting in less products potentially going to waste to make room for product ranges that attract a higher interest in store visitors.

3.6.10 Specific MultiX features

The following technical challenges have been identified:

- Methods and procedures to coordinate 6G and Wi-Fi sensing in the same TSSA.
- Support to coordinate trusted and non-trusted Wi-Fi sensing.
- Support for multiple sensing modes across 6G and Wi-Fi systems.
- Collect and processing of raw 6G and Wi-Fi sensing measurements.
- Fusion of 6G and Wi-Fi sensing data and produce single sensing result to vertical.

3.6.11 Regulatory considerations

This section provides regulatory considerations in respect to GDPR [1], the Data Act [3] and the AI Act [4].

Table 25 presents the GDPR roles and responsibilities for this use case.

Table 25. GDPR Roles and Responsibilities in the Smart Shopping Tracker Use Case

Role	Who	Description
Data Subject	Individuals inside the shop	These are the customers whose location and movement data are collected through sensing-enabled 6G and Wi-Fi devices while they move through the store
Data Controller	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MNO A • MNO B • SENSOR 	These entities jointly determine the purposes and means of processing personal data for the sensing-based analytics service. Each one defines part of the processing chain – e.g., the MNOs handle sensing and fusion of network data, while SENSOR determines how the results are aggregated and visualized for retailers

Data Processor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MNO A MNO B SENSOR 	<p>In some cases, these entities also act as processors for one another, depending on contractual arrangements – e.g., SENSOR might process fused data on behalf of the MNOs, or vice versa, depending on who exposes and controls the sensing results</p>
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Table 26 shows the key aspects of the Data Act in relation with this use case.

Table 26. Key Aspects of the Data Act and Description in Relation to the Smart Shopping Tracker Use Case

Aspect	Description
Fair Access and Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The shop owner (the user of the sensing service) has the right to access aggregated, non-personal insights derived from the sensing data collected in their own store MNO A and MNO B, which operate the 6G and Wi-Fi infrastructure, must not unreasonably restrict or monopolize access to the data that results from shoppers' movements inside the store SENSOR, as a third-party analytics provider, shall be able to obtain that data from the MNOs through transparent and fair-use contracts, ensuring that the terms are not abusive toward smaller service providers or retailers
Data Sharing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MNO A and MNO B collect raw 6G and Wi-Fi sensing data (radio reflections, device presence, positioning).and offer sensing results to third parties In this use case, SENSOR is the third party and processes these data into heatmaps and analytics for the shop owner. Sharing therefore takes place between network operators (data holders) and the analytics provider (data user) – a core scenario envisioned by the Data Act
Consumer Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Shoppers (individuals) generate data through their movement and presence in the store, captured by 6G and Wi-Fi sensing systems operated by the MNOs. Retailers (shop owners), as consumers of the sensing service, also generate data through their store's connected infrastructure

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The consumer rights for the shop owner is to switch to another competitor of SENSOR offering a similar service and to take the data collected about the shop with them
<p>Business Protections</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The shop owner must be able to access aggregated sensing insights without being locked into an exclusive contract with SENSOR SENSOR, as a smaller analytics company, must be protected from dominant operators dictating unfair commercial conditions around pricing, contract length or MNO switching
<p>Interoperability</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6G network operators (MNO A, MNO B), the analytics provider (SENSOR), and retailers must exchange sensing data through common, open, and machine-readable APIs and data formats The sensing data collection and fusion of 6G and Wi-Fi sensing data must follow shared technical standards so that any authorized actor offering sensing entities such as UEs, Base Stations, Wi-Fi Stations and Wi-Fi APs can develop products for the purpose of sensing

Table 27 provides the risk classification of the sensing data processing in this use case in relation with the AI Act.

Table 27. AI-Enabled Technologies in the Smart Shopping Tracker Use Case and their Risk Classification

Technology Enabled by AI	Risk Classification	Explanation
<p>Sensing Data Processing</p>	<p>Limited Risk</p>	<p>The processing of collected sensing data from the cellular and Wi-Fi infrastructure will greatly benefit from AI approaches for target object classification purposes. As the sensing results are providing insights into human presence information and movement patterns within the shop only, there is a limited risk to society and humans visiting the shop</p>

4 Consolidated KPIs

This section aggregates the KPIs defined across all MultiX use cases into a unified view. The consolidated KPIs provide a baseline for evaluating sensing and communication performance in 6G ISAC scenarios. These KPIs cover positioning accuracy, velocity estimation, sensing resolution, latency, refresh rate, and reliability metrics. It enumerates all use cases defined for the project, identifying their leading partner, location where they apply and technology used to enable them.

Table 28 provides a comprehensive overview of the various technologies implemented across the different MultiX use cases, highlighting the diversity of approaches and technical solutions adopted within the framework.

Table 28. Overview of Location and Sensing Technologies Across all MultiX Use Cases

	Industrial Collaborative Robots	Contact-free human localization and respiration detection	Smart Home Virtual Security	Low-altitude UAV management	Gesture Recognition in Industrial Environments	Smart Shopping Tracker
Lead	Siemens	KU Leuven	OTE	Telefonica	Siemens	InterDigital
Location	Indoors	Indoors	Indoors/Outdoors	Outdoors	Outdoors	Indoors
Technology	Cellular, Wireless, Radar, Camera	Cellular, LiDaR, Radar, Camera, Wi-Fi	Cellular, Wi-Fi, Camera	Cellular, Radar, Camera,	Cellular, LiDaR, Radar, Camera,	Cellular, Wi-Fi

Table 29 presents a consolidated summary of all KPIs defined for each individual use case, organized into representative ranges to facilitate comparison and analysis.

D1.1 MultiX Perception 6G use cases, reference scenarios, requirements, and KPIs

Table 29. Consolidated Performance Requirements of MultiX Use cases

Confidence Level [%]	Accuracy of positioning		Accuracy of velocity		Sensing Resolution		Max. Sensing Service Latency [s]	Refresh Rate [s]	Missed Detection [%]	False Positive [%]
	Horizontal [m]	Vertical [m]	Horizontal [m/s]	Vertical [m/s]	Range Resolution [m]	Velocity Resolution [m/s]				
[95-99.999]	[0.1-1]	[0.1-1]	[0.1-1]	[0.1-1]	[0.1-0.5]	[0.1-1]	[0.01-2]	[0.02-1]	[0.1-10]	[1-3]

5 Conclusions

The MultiX project presents a transformative vision for the future of 6G networks by integrating sensing and communication into a unified, intelligent and modern RAN architecture. This deliverable outlines six representative use cases covering the industrial, residential, healthcare, retail, and aerial domains. Each use case demonstrates the potential of ISAC technologies to enhance situational awareness, enable context-aware services, and support real-time decision-making across diverse environments.

Through the definition of reference scenarios, service flows, functional and performance requirements, this document provides a comprehensive framework for the technical development of the MP6R. The inclusion of KPIs and KVIs ensures that both technical efficiency and societal impact are considered in the design and evaluation of future 6G networks, while it is established a sustainable and inclusive 6G ecosystem that addresses real-world challenges and aligns with European regulation.

All in all, the described use cases introduce innovations that underscore the significance of integrating multi-band, multi-static, and multi-technology approaches to attain high-resolution perception and resilient system performance. In addition, the role of the DASH is fundamental to guarantee secure data access, processing, and exposure across the RAN, enabling privacy-preserving mechanisms and trustworthiness for all sensing-driven services. DASH ensures that the integration of perception capabilities is complemented by robust data governance, supporting compliance with GDPR, Data Act and AI Act while fostering innovation through controlled and secure data sharing.

As the project progresses into subsequent work packages, the insights and requirements defined in this deliverable will guide the development of the system architecture, PoCs trials and standardization contributions.

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